

TRANS

lighthouses

MORE THAN GREEN

Lighthouses
of transformative
nature-based solutions
for inclusive communities

Funded by
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Introduction to the TRANS-lighthouses project

TRANS-lighthouses is a project funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement No. 101084628 by the European Union.

The project seeks to collect and analyze both tangible and intangible outcomes of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), with the goal of rethinking and reframing the key components involved in creating socially and ecologically just NBS. Rather than merely guiding the process, collaborative planning and implementation of NBS can foster more unified and effective responses to environmental and climate crises. This, in turn, helps to deepen stakeholder engagement and broaden their capacity for action.

Adopting a non-linear and flexible approach, TRANS-lighthouses embraces a dynamic framework that accommodates the diversity of people, institutions, knowledge systems, practices, and values involved in NBS. The project's overarching ambition is to become a European benchmark for addressing the socio-political dimensions of NBS initiatives, ensuring that these considerations are firmly embedded in the public agenda and contribute to systemic change.

To achieve this, the project will evaluate the benefits and challenges of co-created NBS that have already been implemented. It will also develop, test, and promote guidelines for fair and inclusive NBS implementation from both economic and social perspectives. This work is grounded in a transdisciplinary methodology and critical analysis.

TRANS-lighthouses brings together a robust, cross-border network of citizens, local governments, research institutions, and civil society organizations. By operating across disciplines and sectors, this network will drive research and action aimed at enabling the socio-economic and political transformations necessary for a socially and ecologically just adoption of NBS.

The project spans a network of NBS lighthouse sites across 10 EU countries and 6 non-EU countries, covering urban, rural, coastal, and forested regions.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.5 and its correlated task T2.3 aim to develop a comprehensive typology of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) by categorizing them according to their territorial contexts and anthropogenic characteristics. This typology will serve as a foundational tool for understanding how different types of NBS function across diverse landscapes—urban, rural, coastal, and forested—as well as how they interact with human activities, social structures, and built environments. By systematically identifying and classifying these variations, D2.5

will support more context-sensitive planning, implementation, and evaluation of NBS. It will also contribute to the development of adaptable strategies that acknowledge both environmental and socio-cultural specificities, thereby enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of NBS in addressing climate and ecological challenges.

This task (T2.3) and connected deliverable (D2.5) aim to explore and define the concept of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) Lighthouses — exemplary projects that serve as guiding references for the application of NBS across diverse territorial and urban contexts. Building on interdisciplinary theoretical perspectives and contextual analysis, the work will identify the potential of NBS lighthouses/exemplary projects to address environmental and social challenges at multiple scales.

The initiative will classify design criteria for NBS lighthouses based on natural and human-made morphologies, such as material and immaterial categories, environmental conditions, and sustainability objectives. A key output will be the development of a toolbox for analyzing different types of NBS lighthouses and a portfolio of conceptual and design-based solution-sets. These outputs aim to support orientation among a wide array of coastal, forest, rural, and urban NBS implementations.

Drawing upon prior findings (Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, Task 5.1 and 5.2), the analysis will utilize diagrams, schemes, and data-driven tools to cross-reference pilot projects with assessment cases, supporting an integrated understanding of how NBS can effectively address urgent environmental issues. The work will also incorporate insights from general theoretical frameworks to inform considerations of scale, sustainability, energy, and climate adaptation. The task uses a text analysis evaluation of descriptive narrative contents provided by the Pilot Cases and the Assessment Cases.

This report examines the challenges and opportunities in applying typological classifications to Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), emphasizing their inherently complex and multi-dimensional nature. While typologies provide a useful framework for analyzing and comparing NBS, the study highlights that no single category can fully capture the diverse social, environmental, cultural, and economic dimensions each solution entails.

The analysis identifies key patterns and gaps across territorial typologies—urban, rural, forestry, and coastal. Urban areas are the most represented, reflecting a focus on sustainability in dense environments, while coastal and forest-exclusive typologies are underrepresented, pointing to areas for future research. Hybrid typologies acknowledge the overlapping nature of socio-ecological systems.

Flexibility in territorial classification is shown to be crucial, as demonstrated by the Cáceres case, which shifted from urban to rural classification in response to governance needs, leading to improved community engagement.

The report also distinguishes between material and immaterial NBS, noting that rural areas tend to prioritize social and cultural interventions, while urban settings focus more on physical infrastructure. Across all typologies, environmental sustainability is a primary goal, often intersecting with cultural, social, and economic objectives—though few cases address all four sustainability pillars simultaneously.

Finally, the integration of URBINAT¹ categories reveals a strong presence of social, participatory, and solidarity economy aspects, especially in rural and mixed settings, while technological innovation remains limited to urban/coastal contexts.

This typology-driven analysis contributes to a more holistic understanding of NBS, offering insights to guide context-sensitive planning and more integrated, inclusive implementation strategies.

¹ <https://urbinat.eu/nbs-catalogue/>

SECTION

1. The importance of Typologies in NBS

A NBS definition endorsed by the European Commission and approved by the United Nation Environment Assembly (UNEA-5), fifth session (UNEP, 2022), defines NBS as: 'actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits'.

Within this definition typologies play a critical role in the conceptualization, implementation, and evaluation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). They offer a structured framework to classify and differentiate diverse approaches that leverage natural processes to address societal challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and urbanization.

Typology, in the context of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), refers to the systematic classification of different NBS interventions into distinct categories based on shared characteristics, functions, or territorial and anthropogenic features. This classification serves as an essential analytical tool in both academic and practical domains, enabling stakeholders to make sense of the complex and varied forms that NBS can take across different ecological and social landscapes.

By organizing NBS into structured types—whether based on ecosystem types (e.g., wetlands, forests, urban green spaces), intended functions (e.g., climate regulation, flood management, social inclusion), or the degree of human intervention—typologies help simplify and clarify the diverse range of practices encompassed by the concept of NBS. They provide a coherent framework that supports comparative analysis, allows for the identification of best practices, and aids in theoretical development by highlighting patterns, relationships, and gaps within and across cases.

In applied research and policy-making, an NBS typology facilitates more targeted and context-sensitive planning, ensuring that solutions are appropriately matched to local environmental conditions and societal needs. It also fosters cross-disciplinary dialogue by offering a common language to describe and assess NBS, and supports scalability and replicability by distinguishing which types are most effective in particular settings. Ultimately, developing a robust typology of NBS contributes to building a more systematic, evidence-based foundation for advancing socially and ecologically just nature-based interventions.

Firstly, typologies facilitate clarity and consistency in terminology, which is essential for interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange among scientists, policymakers, and practitioners. Given the broad and evolving nature of NBS, a clear typological framework helps delineate what constitutes an NBS, distinguishing it from conventional engineering or purely conservation-based interventions.

Secondly, typologies enhance the scalability and transferability of NBS by allowing for the comparison of case studies across different geographic, ecological, and socio-political contexts. This comparative perspective supports evidence-based decision-making and the formulation of best practices.

Thirdly, typologies support policy development and governance by aligning specific types of NBS with regulatory frameworks, funding mechanisms, and strategic goals. For example, distinguishing between green infrastructure, ecosystem restoration, and urban greening enables targeted policy instruments and performance indicators.

Lastly, typologies aid in monitoring and evaluation, as they provide criteria for assessing the ecological, social, and economic outcomes of different NBS types. This is particularly important for measuring co-benefits and trade-offs, thus contributing to adaptive management strategies.

1.1. Typologies: why?

Typology refers to the systematic classification of phenomena into distinct types or categories based on shared characteristics or defining features. In academic discourse, typologies are analytical tools used to simplify complex realities by organizing diverse elements into coherent structures, thereby facilitating comparison, interpretation, and theoretical development.

Typologies serve several critical functions in scholarly research. Firstly, they provide conceptual clarity, enabling researchers to delineate boundaries within a field of study and to distinguish between different manifestations of a phenomenon. For instance, in the social sciences, typologies are frequently employed to differentiate governance models, institutional arrangements, or policy approaches.

Secondly, typologies contribute to theoretical generalization by identifying patterns or regularities across cases. This allows scholars to move beyond idiosyncratic observations and toward broader explanatory frameworks.

Thirdly, typologies function as heuristic devices, guiding empirical inquiry and hypothesis formation. By establishing predefined categories, typologies help in structuring data collection and analysis, particularly in comparative and case study research.

It is important to note that typologies are not fixed or absolute; rather, they are context-dependent constructs that reflect the assumptions, goals, and epistemological orientations of the researcher. As such, their development requires careful consideration of the criteria for classification, the internal consistency of categories, and their relevance to the research objectives.

In summary, typology is a fundamental methodological and theoretical instrument in academic research, used to classify, interpret, and analyze complex phenomena in a systematic and meaningful way.

1.2 Current trends in classification of NBS

As Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) gain increasing recognition as multifunctional strategies for addressing environmental and societal challenges, the need for coherent and systematic classification frameworks has become more urgent. The diversity of NBS applications across different ecological, social, and spatial contexts has led to the emergence of various typologies in recent literature. These classifications aim not only to organize the wide range of interventions under the NBS umbrella but also to support effective planning, implementation, and evaluation. This section explores current trends in the classification of NBS, highlighting key dimensions such as type of intervention, scale, governance models, targeted ecosystem services, degree of naturalness, and implementation context.

- Type of Intervention

The IUCN categorizes NBS into five broad types: ecosystem restoration approaches, issue-specific ecosystem-related approaches, infrastructure-related approaches, ecosystem-based management approaches, and ecosystem protection approaches (Anderson and Gough, 2022).

- Targeted Ecosystem Services

A typology for urban Green Infrastructure emphasizes the importance of aligning NBS with specific ecosystem services, such as regulating, provisioning, and cultural services. (Jones et al., 2022, Abson, 2014, Bennett, 2009)

- Scale

FEMA identifies NBS applications at various scales, including neighbourhood or site scale, watershed or landscape scale, and coastal areas, highlighting the adaptability of NBS to different spatial contexts. (Anderson and Gough, 2022, Schumacher, 2012).

- Governance Model

The IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions outlines criteria emphasizing inclusive, transparent, and participatory governance structures, acknowledging the role of community-led and public-private partnerships in NBS implementation. (IUCN, 2020, FEMA 2021)

- Degree of Naturalness

The IUCN's classification includes both natural infrastructure (e.g., forests, wetlands) and green infrastructure (e.g., green roofs, rain gardens), reflecting a spectrum from fully natural to engineered ecosystems. (Anderson and Gough, 2022).

- Implementation Context

The IUCN Global Standard emphasizes the importance of context-specific NBS, adaptable to various social and ecological settings, including urban and rural environments across different geographic regions. (IUCN, 2020, Nehren et al. 2023, Cohen-Shacham et al. 2016)

While the classification proposed in the referenced articles represent an important contribution, it must be emphasized that it constitutes only few of the many possible typologies for categorizing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). However, broader academic literature highlights that NBS can be categorized based on a variety of alternative criteria, depending on the specific focus of analysis.

For instance, Nehren et al. (2023) propose a classification system rooted in disaster risk reduction objectives, emphasizing the protective and adaptive functions of NBS in mitigating natural hazards. Similarly, Cohen-Shacham et al. (2016) offer a typology based on the societal challenges addressed by NBS, such as climate change adaptation, human health, food security, and economic development.

It is important to note that the reviewed state-of-the-art typologies, including the one presented in the aforementioned article, do not incorporate a classification of NBS according to their material (e.g., projects in the built or natural environment) or immaterial (e.g., processes, associations, networking etc) dimensions. Moreover, they do not systematically engage with the territorial aspects of NBS, such as the influence of specific geographical, socio-economic, or ecological contexts on their design and implementation. Addressing these dimensions is crucial for a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the diverse manifestations and impacts of Nature-Based Solutions.

2. Definitions

2.1. Material and Immaterial NBS Definitions

For the purpose of this research some definitions are required to better understand and share the limits and the characteristics of some topics that will be covered in this report.

Definition of Immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (Immaterial NBS)

"Immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (Immaterial NBS) refer to non-physical, procedural-based interventions that enhance human well-being, natural conservation and enhancement, nature-human relationships, social cohesion, and environmental sustainability through knowledge dissemination, behavioral change, cultural practices, and governance mechanisms. These solutions leverage ecological principles to foster education, awareness, community engagement, and policy development without requiring significant material infrastructure."

Raymond et al. (2017) define NBS as actions inspired by nature that provide environmental, social, and economic benefits. Immaterial NBS, in particular, focus

on cultural, educational, and governance-based interventions rather than physical infrastructure.

Eggermont et al. (2015) highlight the role of NBS in fostering social well-being and education, recognizing that interventions such as environmental awareness programs and participatory governance are crucial in integrating nature into society.

Albert et al. (2019) discuss the intangible benefits of nature-based solutions, emphasizing that beyond physical interventions like green infrastructure, knowledge-sharing, co-design processes, and social innovation are fundamental to ensuring long-term success.

Definition of "Material Nature-Based Solutions (Material NBS)

Definition of "Material Nature-Based Solutions (Material NBS) refer to physical, nature-inspired interventions designed to address environmental and societal challenges by leveraging ecosystem processes. These solutions include tangible infrastructure, such as green roofs, urban forests, permeable surfaces, and wetland restoration, which provide measurable ecological, social, and economic benefits while enhancing climate resilience and biodiversity."

IUCN (2020) defines NBS as actions that protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems to address societal challenges. Material NBS specifically refer to physical interventions, such as urban green spaces or coastal protection structures, that provide direct ecosystem services.

European Commission (2015) categorizes NBS into different types, highlighting the role of engineered green infrastructure (e.g., green roofs, constructed wetlands) as a key component of Material NBS.

Cohen-Shacham et al. (2016) emphasize that Material NBS include solutions that physically modify landscapes or urban environments to enhance resilience, reduce flooding, and improve biodiversity.

2.2. Territorial Typologies Definitions

Forestry Definition:

Forestry areas refer to landscapes dominated by forests or woodland ecosystems, including both managed and natural forests. In the context of NBS, these areas are leveraged for ecosystem restoration, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable resource use. Typical interventions include reforestation, afforestation, and integrated forest landscape management. European Commission (2021).

Coastal Definition:

Coastal territories are located along the land-sea interface and encompass features such as beaches, dunes, estuaries, and coastal wetlands. These areas are particularly susceptible to climate-related risks including sea-level rise and storm surges. NBS in coastal zones focus on enhancing natural buffers—such as

mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes—to mitigate erosion, reduce flood risks, and support marine biodiversity. European Commission (2021).

Urban Definition:

Urban areas are densely built environments with high population concentrations and extensive infrastructure. In urban contexts, NBS aim to address challenges like stormwater runoff, air pollution, biodiversity loss, and the urban heat island effect. Common solutions include green roofs, permeable surfaces, urban tree planting, and the creation of green and blue infrastructure networks. European Commission (2015).

Rural Definition:

Rural areas are sparsely populated regions typically dominated by agricultural, pastoral, or natural landscapes. NBS in these areas support sustainable land management, water conservation, and biodiversity enhancement. They also play a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem services that benefit both local communities and broader environmental health. European Commission (2023).

Semi-Rural Definition:

Semi-rural areas are transitional zones between urban and rural environments, often featuring a mix of built infrastructure and open or agricultural land. These areas may experience urban sprawl or peri-urban development. NBS in semi-rural contexts often address land fragmentation, habitat connectivity, and landscape multifunctionality—balancing ecological, social, and economic functions.

European Commission (2021).

3. Methodology

For the purpose of this report, the research group developed a structured table/matrix designed to systematically collect information from the pilot and assessment cases within the project. The primary objective was to obtain comparable qualitative data concerning the key aspects that characterize Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) across diverse contexts.

To guide data collection, the matrix was structured around questions that would define the principal characteristics of the NBS:

- **Who:** Identifying the stakeholders involved in the co-creation processes, as well as those affected by the implementation of the NBS.
- **Where:** Determining the territorial typology or context in which the NBS is implemented.
- **What:** Describing the type of solutions being co-created and co-implemented.

- **When:** This category was deemed less relevant, as all pilot and assessment cases are either currently ongoing or were recently completed.
- **Why:** Understanding the underlying goals, motivations, and intended outcomes driving the co-creation of NBS.

An additional entry was incorporated into the table to identify which of the territorial categories proposed by the URBiNAT project best aligned with the specific characteristics of each pilot and assessment case. This inclusion aimed to build upon an existing typological framework, philologically close to the nature of this project, thereby enriching the analysis with a comparative lens and offering further contextual insights into the nature of each case.

The matrix was distributed to all pilot and assessment cases. Upon receiving their responses, the research team conducted a review to identify gaps, inconsistencies, or unclear information, and followed up with additional inquiries to pilot and assessment cases where necessary.

Subsequently, the methodology and preliminary findings were presented to the Work Package (WP) leaders for review and feedback. Furthermore, the approach and results were shared in a dedicated workshop with representatives from the pilot and assessment cases. Comments and suggestions received during these interactions were incorporated to refine the analysis and enhance the overall quality and robustness of the research outcomes.

3.1. Text Analysis methodology

The Tables/matrixes included in this deliverable were investigated through a text analysis methodology involving a systematic examination and interpretation of the textual data to extract meaningful information. Below is a description of the key steps of this methodology:

Define Objectives: Purpose: the goal was to identify themes and measure frequency of terms.

Data Preparation: Collection: the collection of the textual data, the Tables/matrixes happened in the months of January and February 2025, the eight Pilot and the ten Assessment Caserepresentatives were requested to fill in the tables. Cleaning: the Tables were cleaned of typos, and standardized in the formatting. Organizing: The Tables were subdivided into manageable units of text.

Analysis Techniques: Quantitative Analysis: Frequency Analysis: Measure word or phrase occurrences. Qualitative Analysis: Thematic Coding: Identify and categorize recurring themes. Narrative Analysis: Explore how stories or arguments are structured.

Tools and Software: Manual: Conducted using spreadsheets and word processors.

Interpret Findings: Synthesize Results: Combine insights from different techniques.

Contextualize: Relate findings to the research question or objectives (finding recurring themes and red threads among tables/matrixes).

Reporting: Present the results through visualizations (charts, tables, diagrams) and written summaries.

The text analysis focused on the following aspects:

- **Material and Immaterial NBS**
This distinction highlights the different forms that Nature-Based Solutions can take. Material NBS refer to physical interventions such as green infrastructure, water management systems, or reforestation projects. Immaterial NBS, on the other hand, emphasize non-physical dimensions like community engagement, education, social cohesion, and cultural heritage. Analyzing both types allows for a more complete understanding of how NBS address ecological and social challenges.
- **Stakeholders of Interest**
This aspect identifies the broader group of actors who are affected by or have a vested interest in the NBS initiatives. These may include local communities, policymakers, researchers, businesses, and civil society organizations. Understanding who the stakeholders are is essential for assessing the potential impact, relevance, and sustainability of NBS in a given context.
- **Stakeholders Directly Involved in the Co-Creation Process**
Beyond general interest, this point focuses on those actively participating in the design, development, and implementation of NBS. These stakeholders play a central role in ensuring that solutions are locally grounded, inclusive, and responsive to community needs. Their engagement is key to fostering ownership and long-term success.
- **Territorial Typologies**
This refers to the classification of NBS based on the characteristics of the territories where they are implemented, such as urban, rural, forestry, or coastal environments. By mapping the distribution and performance of NBS across different territorial types, the analysis uncovers how geographical and socio-ecological conditions influence the choice, design, and impact of nature-based interventions.
- **URBINAT Categories**
Derived from the URBINAT project framework, these categories capture cross-cutting themes and values embedded in NBS, such as Social and solidarity economy, Participatory, Technological, Territorial. Applying these categories to the analysis allows for a richer interpretation of the social innovation dimensions that NBS can support.
- **Objectives/Goals Typologies**
This component explores the underlying aims of each NBS initiative, whether focused on environmental sustainability, economic resilience, social inclusion, or cultural preservation. Classifying NBS by their goals helps to clarify their intended outcomes and facilitates comparison across projects and regions, highlighting trends, synergies, and potential gaps in strategic orientation.

4. Analysis

This section presents the analysis of the data collected through the table/matrix distributed to both the assessment cases and the pilot cases. The analysis is structured according to a set of predefined categories aimed at identifying relevant typologies for the classification of Nature-based Solutions (NBS). Specifically, the following analytical dimensions were employed:

- **Material and Immaterial NBS:** This category distinguishes between NBS that involve tangible, physical interventions and those that are primarily based on processes, practices, or intangible activities, thereby offering a deeper understanding of the nature of each solution.
- **Stakeholders of Interest:** This dimension examines the societal groups that the NBS are primarily intended to benefit or address, helping to map the broader societal relevance and inclusivity of the interventions.
- **Stakeholders Directly Involved in the Co-Creation Process:** This aspect focuses on identifying which segments of the population were actively engaged in the co-creation and development of the NBS, highlighting participatory dynamics and the inclusiveness of the design processes.
- **Territorial Typologies:** This category analyzes the type of territorial contexts (urban, peri-urban, rural, coastal, etc.) represented in the projects, allowing for a better understanding of how NBS are adapted to different spatial and environmental conditions.
- **URBiNAT Categories:** By applying the URBiNAT project's classification framework—a sister initiative—this analysis offers a comparative lens to further characterize the nature and scope of the NBS implemented. The URBiNAT categories are the following:
 - Territorial NBS are interventions sustained by nature that will make a significant contribution towards urban biodiversity, urban resilience to climate change, and storm-water management. These solutions promote urban regeneration and entail social and economic benefits through locally adapted implementations of a wide range of ecosystem services.
 - Technological Nature-Based Solutions are characterized by the use of advanced techniques and materials for their design and manufacturing processes and by the integration of ICT systems for their maintenance and monitoring.
 - Social and Solidarity Economy NBS are defined by URBiNAT as opportunities for changing social, political and economic relations among people who live in the neighbourhoods covered by the project. The project recognizes this as part of a broader socio-economy dimension based on practices whose ultimate goal is not profit (or its absence), but solidarity and cooperation.
 - Participatory NBS aim to address the needs, aspirations and knowledge of residents and users of public spaces in URBiNAT intervention areas. The aim of Participatory NBS is to operationalize

the co-creation process by putting in dialogue those needs, aspirations and knowledge with political, technical and scientific views. As URBiNAT operates within an urban governance framework, the main actors to design and implement participatory NBS are residents and users, municipal actors and academic practitioners.

- **Objectives and Goals Typologies:** This category seeks to identify the primary challenges and aspirations that the NBS aim to address, such as climate resilience, social cohesion, biodiversity enhancement, or health improvement.

Through the application of these categories, the analysis seeks to construct a nuanced set of typologies that capture the diversity, intent, and operational characteristics of the NBS under investigation.

4.1. Immaterial and Material NBS

This paragraph examines the relationship between material and immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) within the project.

In the analysis of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), the distinction between material and immaterial approaches serves as a useful lens through which to understand the different dimensions and impacts of NBS initiatives. However, it is essential to recognize that these are not fixed or mutually exclusive categories, but rather perspectives that reflect the entry point or primary focus of a given solution.

Material NBS are typically associated with tangible, physical interventions in the environment. These may include green infrastructure such as parks, urban forests, rain gardens, permeable pavements, or river restoration. The emphasis is often on visible, ecological transformations—addressing issues like climate adaptation, biodiversity enhancement, or flood control through concrete, place-based measures.

Immaterial NBS, by contrast, center on intangible elements such as community building, cultural identity, local knowledge, education, governance, and social cohesion. These solutions often manifest through processes like participatory planning, environmental education programs, cultural regeneration activities, or initiatives that strengthen networks of trust and collective action.

Crucially, this distinction is not absolute. Many NBS that begin from an immaterial starting point—such as building community awareness or fostering social networks—ultimately lead to material outcomes, like the creation of a community garden or the revitalization of public space. Conversely, materially focused NBS often have profound immaterial impacts, such as fostering a sense of belonging, improving mental health, or reshaping social dynamics within a neighborhood.

This interdependence underscores the dynamic and evolving nature of NBS. The material and immaterial aspects are interwoven, often reinforcing each other in a virtuous cycle of transformation. As such, rather than categorizing NBS rigidly, it is more appropriate to view them along a continuum, where the emphasis can shift over time depending on local needs, stakeholder engagement, and contextual factors.

Recognizing this fluidity encourages a more holistic understanding of NBS and highlights the importance of considering both physical and social dimensions in their planning, implementation, and evaluation. It also invites practitioners and policymakers to remain open to the co-evolution of ecological and social systems, ensuring that nature-based interventions contribute not only to environmental goals but also to the transformation of social structures, relationships, and values.

As shown in the pie chart (Figure 3), there is minimal dominance of material NBS over immaterial NBS among the pilot and assessment cases of the TRANS-Lighthouses project. Furthermore, the analysis highlights the existence of distinct categories within both material and immaterial NBS, as well as their respective distributions across the project's pilot and assessment cases.

Category name of Immaterial NBS	Inputs from text	Pilots									Assessments										TOTAL x category		
		Estarreja	Barcelons	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Caceres	TOTAL	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon-Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelons	Uppera Allgu	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja		TOTAL x Line	
Strategies for Promotion and Conservation of Natural Values	strategy for promotion and conservation of natural values	1								1											1	11	
	BioRia, a Nature Tourism and Environmental Education project.	1								1											1		
	BioRia program focused on Nature Tourism, Environmental Education and Nature Conservation.																			1	1		
	Environmental education	1								1										1	2		
	Tourist education	1								1													1
	Biodiversity conservation/enhancement	1			1	1				4										1	5		
Territorial Assessment and Planning	co-diagnostic of the territory	1								1											1	3	
	definition of frameworks/strategies for the future work on local natural patrimony	1								1											1		
	A priority map identifying areas with the greatest flooding risks.										1										1		
Community Engagement	Co-create playground spaces through Nature-Based Solutions (NBS).		1							1											1	4	
	Living Knowledge Lab for Regenerative Knowledge and Practice (farming initiatives)							1						1							2		
	Communal maintenance of mountain terraces.																1				1		
Management and Prevention	deploying and monitoring the Municipal Water Plan (PCE).											1									1	7	
	multifunctional forest management.															1					1		
	creating value chains for forest products															1					1		
	Integrated Stormwater Management								1	1											1		

	sustainable water management.																			1	1		
	Decentralised composting for organic waste																					1	2
Knowledge Sharing and Knowledge Production	Knowledge platform																				1	1	
	An institutional framework needs to be developed to oversee dry-stone wall construction training activities.																					1	1
	using local expert knowledge to maintain and transfer the traditional knowledge of dry stone wall construction.																					1	1

Table 1: Immaterial NBS, collection of inputs coming from Table/Matrix filled in by assessment case and pilot cases

Figure 1: Immaterial NBS Pie Chart, percentage of different categories of immaterial NBS in Pilot and Assessment Cases

The pie chart illustrates how different categories of immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are distributed across the pilot cases and assessment cases within the TRANS-Lighthouses project. It is divided into five color-coded sections, each representing a specific category:

- Strategies for Promotion and Conservation of Natural Values represent the largest share at 39.3%, indicating that nearly two-fifths of the cases focus on developing or enhancing strategies to promote and conserve natural ecosystems and biodiversity.
- Management and Prevention accounts for 25.0%, showing a strong emphasis on actions related to managing and preventing environmental risks or degradation.
- Community Engagement makes up 14.3%, reflecting efforts to involve local communities actively in the development and implementation of NBS initiatives.
- Both Territorial Assessment and Planning and Knowledge Sharing and Knowledge Production contribute equally, each at 10.7%. These categories highlight the importance of spatial analysis for planning purposes and the role of knowledge exchange and co-creation in advancing NBS practices.

Overall, the chart suggests that strategic conservation and practical management dominate the focus areas, while community involvement, planning, and knowledge production are also essential but slightly less emphasized.

The pie chart (Figure 2) illustrates the distribution of material Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) categories among the pilot cases and assessment cases in the TRANS-Lighthouses project.

The chart shows that:

- Urban Green Infrastructure and Climate Adaptation constitutes the largest share, accounting for 31.0% of the cases. This suggests a strong focus on creating or enhancing green spaces and integrating climate resilience measures in urban environments.
- Sustainable Land Use and Agriculture and Biodiversity Conservation and Ecological Restoration each represent 20.7% of the cases, highlighting significant attention to sustainable rural practices and ecological recovery efforts.

- Community Engagement and Environmental Education makes up 13.8%, indicating efforts to involve communities and promote environmental awareness through practical, material interventions.
- Urban Planning and Public Space Transformation accounts for 10.3%, suggesting a smaller, though still relevant, focus on redesigning and repurposing urban areas to better align with NBS principles.
- Renewable Energy is present but occupies the smallest share, reflecting a more limited focus on energy-related material NBS within the scope of the project.

Typology name of Material NBS	Inputs from text	Pilots										Assessments										TOTAL by Item	Total XbyCategory	
		Estarreja	Barcelos	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Caceres	Total	Total categories	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon-Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelos	Uppera	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja			
Community Engagement and Environmental Education	Arboretum (in secondary schoolyards)																1						1	4
	"Plantar o Futuro" (Associação Agora Aveiro). students, teachers and staff at the University of Aveiro to adopt a native tree, care for it and plant it	1																					1	
	Natural Playground		1																				1	
	Green Classroom						1																1	
Urban Green Infrastructure and Climate Adaption	introducing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to an existing green belt used as public space				1																		1	9
	Mitigation of heat island effects,				1	1																	2	
	Reduction of flooding,				1							1											2	
	Refuge/enhance for urban biodiversity.				1							1											2	

	conserve biodiversity and restore areas of high ecological value.preserve the cultural and historical heritage of Estarreja.)																						
--	---	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Table 2: Material NBS collection of inputs coming from Table/Matrix filled in by assessment case and pilot cases

- Community Engagement and Environmental Education
- Urban Green Infrastructure and Climate Adaptation
- Urban Planning and Public Space Transformation
- Renewable Energy
- Sustainable Land Use and Agriculture
- Biodiversity Conservation and Ecological Restoration

Figure 2: Material NBS Pie Chart, categories distribution among Pilot and Assessment Cases

Overall, the distribution emphasizes a priority towards green infrastructure, sustainable land use, and biodiversity conservation, while also recognizing the role of community engagement, urban planning, and renewable energy in advancing material NBS initiatives.

Figure 3: Immaterial/Material NBS Pie Chart, distribution among Pilot and Assessment Cases

4.2. Stakeholders of interest

This paragraph examines the diverse nature of the stakeholders targeted by the co-creation activities of the Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), specifically those stakeholders identified as relevant to each NBS. As will be discussed in the following paragraph, these stakeholders may or may not coincide with those who are actively involved in the co-creation process.

Definition of the categories of stakeholder identified for grouping the inputs coming from the pilot cases and assessment cases in their Matrix/tables:

Locals/Individual Residents

Community members and citizens living in or near the area where the NBS is implemented. They hold vital local knowledge and are often the direct users, stewards, and beneficiaries of NBS initiatives. Their engagement ensures solutions are adapted to real local needs and contexts.

Education (Primary, Secondary)

Schools, students, and educational staff at primary and secondary levels. They play a role in raising environmental awareness, building a culture of sustainability from a young age, and often participate through educational programs linked to NBS projects.

Tertiary/Vocational Education

Institutions of higher learning (universities, technical colleges) and vocational training centers. They contribute through research, technical knowledge, capacity building, innovation, and training the next generation of NBS practitioners and advocates.

Leisure/Tourism/Wellbeing Stakeholders

Organizations, businesses, and individuals related to recreation, tourism, and wellness sectors. They have an interest in how NBS enhance the attractiveness, health benefits, and recreational value of places, promoting both environmental and economic sustainability.

Vulnerable Groups

Communities or individuals at greater risk of environmental, social, or economic marginalization (e.g., low-income groups, elderly, minorities, disabled individuals). Their inclusion in NBS projects is critical for ensuring social equity, justice, and resilience.

Artists

Creative practitioners including visual artists, performers, and designers who contribute by enhancing the cultural and aesthetic dimensions of NBS. Their involvement fosters community engagement, storytelling, and emotional connection to the natural environment.

Authorities

Governmental bodies and public sector institutions at local, regional, or national levels. They provide regulatory frameworks, policy support, funding opportunities, and governance structures necessary for enabling, legitimizing, and scaling up NBS.

NGOs/Civil Society Organizations

Non-governmental organizations and civil society groups that advocate for environmental and social issues. They often act as bridges between local communities and institutions, facilitate community organization, and contribute expertise in project implementation and monitoring.

Business/Economy Stakeholders

Private sector actors such as companies, business associations, and entrepreneurs. They can support NBS through funding, innovation, services, or integration into corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies, aligning economic interests with ecological benefits.

Associate Professionals Group

Technical and professional experts such as urban planners, landscape architects, engineers, and consultants. They play key roles in designing, implementing, and maintaining NBS, translating community visions and policy goals into practical, functional interventions.

Group name	Inputs from text	Pilots										Assessments											
		Estarreja	Barcelona	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Caceres	TOTAL (pilots)	TOTAL CATEGORIES (pilots)	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon-Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelona	Uppera Allgäu	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja	TOTAL Assessments	
Locals individual residences	Families				1					1	7			1				1					2
	Local communities/Citizens/Private housing owners	1		1	1			1		4		1	1	1	1					1	1		6
	Residents of rural communities							1		1						1							1
	Social housing tenants								1	1													0
Education (Primary, Secondary)	Students (Primary, secondary, highschool)	1	1	1		1				4	5						1	1					2
	teachers				1					1													0
Tertiary/vocational education	Students (University)				1		1			2	2			1						1			2
	Researchers/Academia									0										1			1
Leisure/Tourism/wellbeing	Hikers/Cyclists/Joggers				1	1				2	4								1		1		2
	People looking to reconnect with nature/benefit from eco therapies, (e.g. forest bathing);									0											1		1
	Tourists				1	1				2				1						1		1	
Vulnerable groups	Homelesses				1					1	6												0
	Drug Users				1					1													0
	Social Services Clients				1					1													0
	Youth					1	1		1	3										1			
Artists	Artists				1					1	1												0
Authorities	Authorities/Municipality/public services					1				1	1	1									1		2
NGOs/Civil Society	NGOs / Civil Society					1				1	1	1								1			2
Business/economy stakeholders	Consumers								1	1	2						1						1

	Businesses									0									1				
	Farmers						1			1							1		1	1			
	Local markets									0										1			
Associate professionals group	Technicians									0										1			
	Practitioners									0								1		1			

Table 3: Categories of Stakeholders of interest for the NBS (that are affected or that can affect the NBS), inputs coming from the Table/Matrix

This pie chart (Figure 4) illustrates the stakeholders of interest affected or that can affect in the co-creation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). Each sector of the chart represents a different group, along with their relative proportion of involvement as defined by the Pilots and Assessments cases. Here's a breakdown of the stakeholder groups and their respective percentages:

- Business/economy stakeholders: 17.9% (largest group)
- Locals (individual residences): 16.1%
- Education (Primary, Secondary): 12.5%
- Vulnerable groups: 12.5%
- Tertiary/vocational education: 8.9%
- NGOs/Civil Society: 5.4%
- Artists: 5.4%
- Authorities: 5.4%
- Leisure/Tourism/Wellbeing: 5.4%
- Associate professionals group: 14.3%

The most prominent stakeholders are *business/economy stakeholders*, followed by *locals* and *education/vulnerable groups*, highlighting the significance of involving both economic and community actors in NBS efforts.

Education sectors (both primary/secondary and tertiary/vocational) collectively form over 21% of the total, showing a strong emphasis on learning and knowledge transfer.

Groups such as *artists*, *NGOs*, *authorities*, and *leisure/tourism* each make up smaller but still meaningful parts, pointing to the interdisciplinary nature of the co-created NBSolutions.

This chart reflects a diverse and balanced stakeholder ecosystem, an essential and wished outcome for an inclusive, sustainable, and context-sensitive implementation of NBS.

- Locals individual residences ● Education (Primary, Secondary) ● Tertiary/vocational education
- Leisure/Tourism/wellbeing ● Vulnerable groups ● Artists ● Authorities
- NGOs/Civil Society ● Business/economy stakeholders ● Associate professionals group

Figure 4: Pie Chart with the percentage of Categories of Stakeholders of interest for the NBS (that are affected or that can affect the NBS)

4.3. Stakeholders directly involved in the co-creation

This section presents an analysis of the distribution of stakeholder groups engaged in the co-creation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) across the pilot and assessment cases of the project. The accompanying table and pie chart illustrate the proportion of involvement by various stakeholder categories, highlighting both the diversity and the areas of focus within the engagement efforts.

Definitions of the groups identified among the different stakeholders mentioned as part of the co-creation process by pilots and assessment cases:

Locals/Individual Residents

People living within or near the intervention area. They are key beneficiaries and users of NBS and often possess valuable local knowledge about the environment and social dynamics. Their engagement ensures NBS reflect local needs and contribute to community ownership.

NGOs/Civil Society

Non-profit organizations, community groups, and advocacy networks focused on social, environmental, or cultural issues. They act as facilitators, advocates, watchdogs, and mobilizers of public participation in NBS planning and implementation processes.

Business/Economy Stakeholders

Private sector entities such as companies, industry groups, and entrepreneurs. Their role includes providing financial support, technical innovation, and integrating NBS into sustainable business models or corporate social responsibility initiatives.

Authorities

Government bodies at local, regional, or national levels. Authorities are essential for policy-making, regulatory approval, funding, public participation management, and long-term stewardship of NBS. They ensure that interventions align with broader urban planning and environmental strategies.

Tertiary/Vocational Education

Universities, colleges, and vocational training institutions. They contribute research, innovation, technical expertise, and training related to NBS, often acting as bridges between scientific knowledge and practical application.

Education (Primary, Secondary)

Schools and educational institutions at the elementary and secondary levels. These stakeholders are important for environmental education and youth engagement, fostering early awareness and stewardship of natural environments.

Associate Professionals Group

Technical experts and practitioners such as urban planners, architects, landscape designers, ecologists, and engineers. They are crucial in designing, implementing, and maintaining effective and sustainable NBS.

Vulnerable Groups

Socially, economically, or physically disadvantaged populations, including the elderly, people with disabilities, minority communities, and low-income groups. Their meaningful participation ensures that NBS promote social equity and resilience.

Animals

Non-human species that form part of the ecosystems targeted by NBS. While not active stakeholders in a conventional sense, their needs must be considered to promote biodiversity, ecosystem health, and humane interactions within NBS frameworks.

Welfare State

Public institutions and services that provide social security, healthcare, education, and housing. Their involvement ensures that NBS projects contribute to broader goals of social wellbeing, public health, and inclusive development.

Group name	Inputs from text	Pilots									Assessments										TOTAL Assessments	Total assessments Categories	TOTAL by CATEGORIES					
		Estarreja	Barcelona	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Caceres	TOTAL	TOTAL PILOTS CATEGORIES	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon-Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelona	Upper Allgäu	Troodos	Lagoa				Estarreja				
Locals/individual residents	Citizens/Private owners	1								2	5			1								1	4	9				
	Social housing tenants									1															0			
	Local community			1	1					2									1						1			
	Families									0				1	1										2			
NGOs/Civil Society	NGOs/civil societies (cultural, social, sporting and environmental, farming associations)	1			1		1			3	3	1	1		1	1					1	1	6	6	9			
Business/economy stakeholders	Local markets									0	4				1							2	7	11				
	Farmers	1					1			2					1	1		1	1						4			
	Local businesses	1								1								1							1			
	Industry	1								1															0			
Authorities	Public authorities/Services	1			1	1				3	9	1										1	10	19				
	Administrations/Municipalities					1	1	1		3			1	1		1		1	1	1					6			
	Political and elected representatives						1	1	1	3					1			1		1					3			
Tertiary/vocational education	Academia/Researchers	1		1		1	1			4	5		1		1		1	1	1			5	7	12				
	Students (university)						1			1			1					1							2			
Education (Primary, Secondary)	Teachers	1	1				1			3	7				1		1	1				3	6	13				
	Students (elementary to highschool)	1	1	1			1			4					1		1	1							3			
Associate professionals group	Technicians	1	1							2	4						1	1				2	3	7				
	Practitioners			1						1								1							1			
	Foresters	1								1															0			

The table and the pie chart below (Figure 5) represent the distribution of stakeholder groups involved in the co-creation of Nature-Based Solutions across the “pilot cases” and “assessment cases” of the project. Each segment indicates the proportion of involvement by different stakeholder categories, highlighting the diversity and focus of engagement efforts.

- Business/economy stakeholders: 21.8%
This is the most involved group, indicating a strong emphasis on integrating economic actors in the co-creation process.
- Education (Primary, Secondary): 14.9%
Significant engagement with the education sector suggests a focus on knowledge-building and youth/community awareness.
- Tertiary/vocational education: 13.8%
Combined with primary/secondary education, this brings the total education-related participation to nearly 29%.
- Associate professionals group: 12.6%
This includes skilled practitioners who likely contribute specific technical or planning expertise.
- Locals: 10.3%
Reflects community-based engagement, crucial for place-based and context-sensitive NBS solutions.
- NGOs/Civil Society: 10.3%
Highlights the role of organized community actors and advocacy groups.
- Authorities: 8.0%
While lower than some other groups, authorities are essential for policy alignment and governance.
- Vulnerable groups: 3.4%
Indicates that while included, there may be room to strengthen their representation.
- Animals: 2.3%
Represents ecological or conservation interests—unique among primarily human-centered categories.
- Welfare State: 2.3%
Involves social institutions possibly focusing on health, social care, and inclusion.

This chart shows a well-rounded stakeholder engagement strategy, with strong representation from the business, education, and professional sectors, and meaningful—but lesser—involvement from locals, NGOs, and public authorities. The low representation of vulnerable groups and non-human entities (like animals) might suggest a need for more inclusive or ecocentric approaches in future co-creation processes.

- Locals
 NGOs/Civil Society
 Business/economy stakeholders
 Authorities
- Tertiary/vocational education
 Education (Primary, Secondary)
- Associate professionals group
 Vulnerable groups
 Animals
 Welfare State

Figure 5: Pie chart with Categories of Stakeholders directly involved in the co-creation process

4.4. Territorial Typology

This section introduces the distribution of territorial typologies represented across the Pilot and Assessment cases within the project. The accompanying pie chart provides an overview of the diverse environments in which Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are being co-created and implemented. The data reveal a predominant focus on rural and urban contexts, which collectively account for more than 64% of the total cases. It is important to note that many cases demonstrate an overlap of multiple territorial typologies, resulting in complex forms of territorial intersections, a phenomenon that will be further explored in the following section. Additionally, the emergence of a new territorial classification, "semi-rural," derived from the project's action descriptions, enhances the ability to more precisely contextualize specific cases, such as the pilot in Roskilde and the assessment case in Denmark. This refinement underscores the project's commitment to accurately capturing the nuances of the territorial contexts in which NBS initiatives are being developed.

(A definition of the territorial typologies can be found in section 2.2)

The pie chart (figure 6) in this paragraph illustrates the distribution of territorial typologies represented in the Pilot cases and Assessment cases of the project, providing insight into the types of environments where Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are being co-created and implemented.

This distribution shows a strong emphasis on rural and urban contexts, which together make up over 64% of the total cases.

It is noteworthy that the majority of the pilot and assessment cases exhibit an overlap of multiple territorial typologies, giving rise to various forms of territorial intersections. This phenomenon will be further illustrated in the following section. Moreover, an additional territorial category—*“semi-rural”*—has emerged from the project's action descriptions. This newly introduced classification proves particularly valuable in more accurately contextualizing specific cases, such as the pilot in Roskilde and the assessment case in Denmark.

TRANS-Lighthouses Typologies	Pilots									Assessments										TOTAL	
	Estarreja	Barcelos	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Cáceres	TOTAL Pilots	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon- Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelos	Upper Allgäu	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja		TOTAL Assessments
Rural	1	1	1			1		1	5			1		1			1	1	1	5	10
Forestry		1	1						2							1	1	1		3	5
Urban		1		1	1		1		4	1	1		1		1					4	8
Coastal			1	1					2									1		1	3
Semi-rural						1			1					1						1	2

Table 5: Typologies of territorial conditions of the pilots and assessment cases, inputs coming from the table/matrix

● Rural ● Forestry ● Urban ● Coastal ● Semi-rural

Figure 6: Pie chart with the percentage of the typologies of territorial conditions of the pilots and assessment cases

4.5. Objectives/goals typologies

In the TRANS-Lighthouses project, the Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) developed across pilot and assessment cases have been co-created through an inclusive, participatory approach involving a wide range of local actors. This section presents an analysis of the objectives and goals emerging from these collaborations, offering insights into the collective visions shaping each initiative. To structure this analysis, the identified objectives have been categorized according to the four pillars of sustainability — social, cultural, environmental, and economic — following the framework proposed by Keith Nurse (2006). This categorization allows for a deeper understanding of how the TRANS-Lighthouses NBS contribute to holistic sustainability, addressing interconnected challenges and opportunities across different local contexts. By mapping these goals, we aim to illuminate the pathways through which the project fosters transformative change at multiple levels.

Economic Sustainability	Cultural Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Environmental Sustainability	Inputs from text	Pilots									TOTAL	Assessments									TOTAL
					Estarreja	Barcelos	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Cáceres	Brussels		Bologna	Moisdon-Larivière	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelos	Upper Allgäu	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja	
	Cultural	Social		Appropriation of natural systems for human recreation;		1							1										0	
	Cultural	Social		Promote intergenerational interaction and integration as an instrument for preserving and enhancing the ecological and cultural heritage of school playgrounds;		1							1										0	
	Cultural	Social	Environmental	Appropriation of natural systems for human recreation;		1							1										0	
	Cultural	Social		Encouraging leadership among young people and the educational community;		1							1										0	
			Environmental	Increasing the environmental resilience of local communities in adapting to climate change;		1							1										0	
	Cultural	Social		Provide creative leisure among students, the ability to play freely and in contact with nature, autonomy in recreational relationships with sustainable playgrounds;		1							1										0	
	Cultural	Social		Diversifying the sources of play and recreation among the youth community;		1							1										0	
	Cultural			Transmitting ancestral knowledge about free play and youth leadership.		1							1										0	
		Social		self-sufficient and eco-community									0										1	

Keith Nurse (2006) argues that sustainable development should be understood as resting on four interdependent pillars, those are the categories that the goals and objective of the pilots and assessment cases are tested against:

- **Economic sustainability** involves maintaining economic growth and development while ensuring equitable distribution of resources and opportunities. It focuses on creating wealth and improving living standards without depleting natural or human resources.
- **Environmental sustainability** stresses the need to protect and responsibly manage natural ecosystems and resources. It emphasizes minimizing environmental degradation and maintaining the health of the planet for current and future generations.
- **Social sustainability** concerns building fair, inclusive, and resilient societies. It emphasizes human rights, social justice, equity, community development, and the strengthening of social cohesion.
- **Cultural sustainability**, the pillar Nurse particularly highlights, recognizes culture as both a driver and enabler of sustainable development. It includes preserving cultural identities, practices, and diversity while fostering creativity, innovation, and community resilience. Nurse argues that cultural vitality underpins social well-being and economic dynamism, and without it, sustainable development efforts are incomplete.

The distribution of the co-created objectives across the four pillars of sustainability is illustrated in the pie chart (figure 8). Environmental sustainability goals represent the largest share, accounting for 36.6% of the total, reflecting a strong focus on ecological resilience and nature conservation across the pilot and assessment cases. Cultural sustainability goals follow with 31.0%, highlighting the importance placed on preserving local identities, traditions, and knowledge systems within the Nature-Based Solutions. Social sustainability goals constitute 20.7%, emphasizing efforts to enhance social inclusion, community well-being, and participatory governance. Finally, economic sustainability goals account for 11.7%, indicating a recognition of the need for financial viability and local economic development, although this pillar was less emphasized compared to the others. Overall, the distribution shows a broad and balanced approach to sustainability, with particular strength in environmental and cultural dimensions.

Figure 8: Pie chart describing the percentages of Objective/goals by four key facets of sustainability

4.6. Current research on NBS typologies: URBINAT Categories

This section presents the responses to the question regarding which URBINAT categories the pilot and assessment cases identified as the most appropriate for classifying their Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). The URBINAT categories² considered are as follows:

Territorial: Territorial NBS are interventions sustained by nature that will make a significant contribution towards urban biodiversity, urban resilience to climate change, and storm-water management. These solutions promote urban regeneration and entail social and economic benefits through locally adapted implementations of a wide range of ecosystem services.

Technological: Technological Nature-Based Solutions are characterized by the use of advanced techniques and materials for their design and manufacturing processes and by the integration of ICT systems for their maintenance and monitoring.

Social and Solidarity Economy: Social and Solidarity Economy NBS are defined by URBINAT as opportunities for changing social, political and economic relations among people who live in the neighbourhoods covered by the project. The project recognizes this as part of a broader socio-economy dimension based on practices whose ultimate goal is not profit (or its absence), but solidarity and cooperation.

Participatory: Participatory NBS aim to address the needs, aspirations and knowledge of residents and users of public spaces in URBINAT intervention areas. The aim of Participatory NBS is to operationalize the co-creation process by putting in dialogue those needs, aspirations and knowledge with political, technical and scientific views. As URBINAT operates within an urban governance framework, the main actors to design and implement participatory NBS are residents and users, municipal actors and academic practitioners.

The pie chart (figure 7) illustrates how the pilot and assessment cases classified their Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) according to the URBINAT project categories. The largest share of responses (36.1%) identified their NBS as belonging to the Territorial category, indicating a predominant focus on spatial and land-related interventions. This is closely followed by the Participatory category at 33.3%, highlighting a strong emphasis on community involvement and co-creation processes. The Social and Solidarity Economy category accounts for 27.8% of the classifications, suggesting a significant, though slightly smaller, focus on promoting inclusive economic practices through NBS. Finally, only a small proportion (around 3%) of cases identified their solutions as Technological, indicating that technology-driven approaches play a relatively minor role compared to social, participatory, and territorial strategies within the project.

² The URBINAT categories can be found at the following link: <https://urbinat.eu/nbs-catalogue/>

This distribution suggests that the TRANS-Lighthouses project primarily fosters socially and territorially embedded NBS, with less emphasis on purely technological innovations.

It is important to note, however, that discussions around technological innovation do not exclusively pertain to ICT technologies. In fields such as design, architecture, and urban planning, technological innovation extends to a wide range of areas, including materials, construction techniques, spatial innovations, funding models, and other related advancements. Therefore, this distribution may look different if the definition of Technology changed.

Inputs from text	Pilots									Assessments										TOTAL Assessments	TOTAL
	Estarreja	Barcelos	Lagoa/Azores	Strovolos	Rome	Roskilde	Brussels	Cáceres	TOTAL Pilots	Brussels	Bologna	Moisdon-Lariviere	Madrid	Denmark	Barcelos	Upper Allgäu	Troodos	Lagoa	Estarreja		
Territorial	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	7	1			1		1	1	1	1		6	13
Technological				1					1											0	1
Social and Solidarity economy	1		1		1	1		1	5			1	1	1		1		1		5	10
Participatory	1		1	1	1		1	1	6		1		1	1			1	1	1	6	12

Table 6: Typologies from URBINAT project, inputs coming from the Table/matrix

● Territorial ● Technological ● Social and Solidarity economy ● Participatory

5. Main Findings and Results

This section presents the results of the analysis conducted on the data collected from both the pilot and assessment cases. The primary aim of this analysis is to explore potential connections—or the absence thereof—between territorial typologies and various other categories identified throughout the pilot and assessment phases. These categories include material and immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), URBINAT categories, stakeholder typologies, and the diverse goals and objectives associated with each case. By examining these relationships, the analysis seeks to uncover underlying patterns and insights that may inform future strategies for integrating NBS in different territorial contexts.

5.1. Territorial typologies

This section provides an in-depth analysis of the distribution of territorial contexts across the pilot and assessment cases involved in the TRANS-Lighthouses project. Understanding how territorial typologies are represented among the cases is essential for interpreting the contextual relevance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and for identifying potential patterns of implementation and impact across different geographical settings.

The territorial typologies adopted by the TRANS-Lighthouses framework are based on four primary classifications: urban, rural, forestry, and coastal. These categories reflect the diverse environmental, socio-economic, and governance conditions within which NBS are developed and implemented. Each typology brings with it a unique set of challenges, priorities, and opportunities for the design and co-production of NBS, as well as different constellations of actors and stakeholder interests.

Urban territories are typically characterized by high population density, significant infrastructure development, and complex governance structures. In such contexts, NBS are often deployed to address challenges such as urban heat islands, air pollution, and social fragmentation, while also contributing to improved quality of life, accessibility to green spaces, and inclusive governance mechanisms. The presence of urban territories among the pilot and assessment cases offers insight into how NBS can respond to the multifaceted pressures of urbanization.

Rural contexts, by contrast, are marked by lower population densities, stronger connections to natural landscapes, and often more traditional or community-based forms of governance. NBS in rural areas may focus more intensively on biodiversity conservation, agricultural sustainability, and the reinforcement of cultural heritage and local knowledge. The representation of rural territories in the case studies provides an opportunity to examine how NBS contribute to ecological restoration while also supporting rural development and resilience.

Forestry areas represent another distinct territorial typology, defined by extensive woodland ecosystems and often linked to conservation and climate mitigation goals. In these settings, NBS initiatives may prioritize forest management, carbon sequestration, and the preservation of ecosystem services, while also navigating issues of land ownership, traditional land use practices, and rural livelihoods. Their inclusion in the TRANS-Lighthouses cases allows for an exploration of the ecological and social co-benefits of forest-related NBS.

Coastal territories, meanwhile, face unique vulnerabilities related to climate change, including sea-level rise, erosion, and saline intrusion. NBS in these areas may involve dune restoration, wetland conservation, or the creation of natural buffers to protect against storm surges. At the same time, coastal areas are often sites of tourism and intensive economic activity, raising important questions about the balance between ecological integrity and economic interests. The coastal cases within the project highlight the potential of NBS to act as adaptive strategies in the face of environmental risks.

Overall, this section aims to map how these four territorial typologies—urban, rural, forestry, and coastal—are distributed across the pilot and assessment cases. By doing so, it seeks to establish a foundational understanding of the territorial contexts in which NBS are embedded, and to set the stage for further analysis of how these contexts influence the types of NBS adopted, the stakeholders involved, and the objectives pursued. This territorial mapping is a crucial step toward identifying both context-specific strategies and transferable insights for the advancement of socially and ecologically just NBS.

Figure 9: Distribution of Pilots and assessments cases according to Territorial Typologies

Territorial typology	Number of Pilot and assessment cases per Territorial Typology
Rural	4
Urban	6
Forestry	1

Costal	0
Rural/Urban/Forestry	1
Rural/Forestry/coastal	2
Urban/coastal	1
Rural/Forestry	1
Rural/Semirural	2

Table 8: Number of Pilots and assessments cases according to Territorial Typologies

The distribution of territorial typologies among the pilot and assessment cases within the TRANS-Lighthouses project reveals a diverse, yet uneven representation of territorial contexts. Among the cases, urban areas are the most frequently represented, with a total of six cases falling under this typology. This indicates a strong emphasis on addressing the challenges and opportunities that urban environments present for the implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), such as managing environmental pressures from dense infrastructure, fostering community well-being, and enhancing green infrastructure.

Rural territories also feature prominently, with four cases categorized strictly as rural. This reflects a significant interest in exploring how NBS can support ecological conservation, local development, and socio-cultural cohesion in less densely populated, often agriculturally oriented regions. Additionally, two cases are defined as rural/semi-rural, suggesting an interest in transitional or peri-urban landscapes where urban and rural characteristics may intersect, potentially requiring hybrid approaches to NBS design.

Mixed or hybrid territorial typologies are also present. Notably, two cases are situated in rural/forestry/coastal settings, while other falls under the rural/urban/forestry category. These configurations suggest more complex territorial dynamics where overlapping ecological and socio-economic systems coexist. Such contexts may provide fertile ground for testing integrative NBS strategies that address multifaceted sustainability challenges.

Other combinations include one rural/forestry case and one urban/coastal case, indicating a more limited representation of forestry and coastal dimensions either independently or in combination with other types. In fact, pure forestry contexts are represented by only one case, and no cases are classified exclusively as coastal. This absence of strictly coastal cases may suggest an area for further exploration, given the pressing environmental vulnerabilities many coastal areas face.

In summary, while urban and rural contexts dominate the distribution, the presence of hybrid typologies such as rural/urban/forestry and rural/forestry/coastal points to the project's recognition of territorial complexity. However, the underrepresentation of pure forestry and the complete lack of standalone coastal cases suggest a potential gap in the current territorial coverage, which may limit the generalizability of findings to those specific environments. This distribution underscores the importance of contextualizing NBS strategies according to the unique characteristics and needs of each territorial setting.

It is also noteworthy that, over the course of the project's development, one of the pilot cases underwent a significant shift in its territorial classification—from urban to rural. This reclassification pertains to the case of Cáceres, which was initially identified as an urban pilot site. However, as the project progressed, the local implementation team encountered persistent challenges in establishing a stable and constructive dialogue with the municipal authorities of the city of Cáceres.

These difficulties, which are elaborated in detail in Annex 8, impeded the intended urban-focused collaboration and limited the project's capacity to mobilize institutional support within the city context.

In response to these obstacles, the local actors strategically redirected their engagement efforts toward smaller towns and rural villages located within the broader territorial area surrounding Cáceres. This adaptive shift resulted in the development of more meaningful, participatory, and context-sensitive interactions with rural stakeholders. These new partnerships proved to be not only more responsive but also more conducive to the co-creation and implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) tailored to rural realities. As a result, the focus of the pilot evolved to better reflect the priorities, challenges, and opportunities of rural territories, leading to its reclassification within the project's territorial typology framework.

5.2. Intersection between Immaterial and Material typologies and territorial typologies

The research undertaken by the TRANS-lighthouses project examines both material and immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to better understand and address the complex interplay between social and ecological justice in creating sustainable and equitable NBS. By exploring both material (e.g., green infrastructure, habitat restoration) and immaterial (e.g., social cohesion, community engagement, cultural heritage) outcomes, the project aims to provide evidence that reframes and broadens our understanding of how NBS can contribute to just and transformative processes in local contexts. This dual focus allows the research to capture a more comprehensive view of the potential of NBS, addressing both the tangible, physical benefits and the intangible, socio-cultural, and governance-related dimensions.

Figure 10: Diagram connecting Immaterial and Material NBS categories to Pilot and Assessment Cas

Territorial typology	Immaterial NBS	Material NBS
Rural	12	8
Urban	6	8
Forestry	2	1
Coastal	0	0
Rural/Urban/Forestry	1	1
Rural/Forestry/coastal	1	1
Urban/coastal	1	9
Rural/Forestry	3	0
Rural/Semirural	2	0

Table 9: Number of Immaterial and Material NBS according to Territorial Typologies

From the data retrieved from the Pilot and Assessment cases in TRANS-Lighthouses it seems that Immaterial Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are most prevalent in rural areas, while the lowest prevalence is observed in Rural/Urban/Forestry, Rural/Forestry/Coastal, and Urban/Coastal settings. The second highest prevalence of immaterial NBS occurs in urban environments. In contrast, material NBS exhibit a more balanced distribution across rural, urban, and rural/forestry settings. These patterns suggest that rural areas are striving to implement a higher quantity of both material and immaterial NBS, whereas urban and urban/coastal areas display a more pronounced emphasis on material NBS over immaterial ones.

5.3. Intersection between Objectives and goals and territorial typologies

This section offers a detailed analysis of the potential relationships between the goals and objectives—referred to in the matrix table as the "motivations" behind the implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)—and the territorial typologies that characterize the pilot and assessment cases. The aim is to investigate whether specific types of goals or intended outcomes are more frequently associated with certain territorial contexts, and to what extent these associations reveal consistent patterns or meaningful divergences.

By examining the motivations behind the NBS initiatives in relation to the distinct territorial classifications—such as rural, urban, coastal, forestry, or hybrid configurations—this analysis seeks to understand how local environmental, social, and economic conditions may shape or influence the prioritization of certain objectives. These objectives may range from ecological restoration and climate resilience to social inclusion, health promotion, or economic regeneration, and their articulation within different territorial settings may reflect the specific challenges, opportunities, and stakeholder dynamics present in each context.

Figure 11: Distribution of Pilots and assessments cases according to the four pillars of sustainability

Figure 12: Distribution of the territorial typologies of the Pilots and assessments cases according to the four pillars of sustainability

The analysis of the goals and objectives articulated across the pilot and assessment cases reveals that the majority are predominantly oriented toward environmental sustainability. This emphasis is especially pronounced in both rural

and urban contexts, where initiatives frequently prioritize ecological concerns such as biodiversity enhancement, climate change mitigation, ecosystem restoration, and green infrastructure development. The centrality of environmental sustainability in these settings suggests a strong alignment with global and local ecological imperatives, regardless of the degree of urbanization.

Notably, a significant intersection between environmental and cultural sustainability emerges in the rural/forestry/coastal pilot and assessment case. In this specific territorial configuration, NBS initiatives often reflect a dual commitment to ecological restoration and the preservation or revitalization of cultural landscapes, traditions, and heritage. This convergence highlights the importance of place-based identities and the recognition of local knowledge systems in shaping the design and implementation of NBS in such areas.

Moreover, a broader overlap encompassing social, cultural, and environmental sustainability is evident in both rural/forestry/coastal and urban pilot and assessment cases. In these contexts, NBS goals frequently integrate objectives related to community well-being, inclusive participation, cultural heritage, and ecological integrity. This multidimensional approach underscores the potential of NBS to serve as integrative tools for addressing interconnected sustainability challenges in complex and diverse socio-territorial environments.

In contrast, goals situated at the interface of social and economic sustainability are found exclusively in rural and semi-rural/rural pilot and assessment cases. In these settings, economic sustainability appears to hold particular significance, with initiatives often aimed at fostering local economic development, sustainable livelihoods, and job creation, alongside promoting social cohesion and equity. The prominence of economic considerations in these rural and semi-rural areas reflects the critical need to align ecological interventions with economic resilience and community empowerment.

The rural/urban/forestry pilot case presents a distinct configuration, wherein the goals are predominantly associated with social and cultural sustainability. Here, the emphasis is placed on fostering social inclusion, participatory governance, and the valorization of cultural practices, suggesting a nuanced understanding of sustainability that prioritizes human and cultural dimensions within a mixed territorial setting.

Furthermore, the intersection of cultural, social, and economic sustainability is present only in a limited number of cases, specifically within rural, semi-rural/rural, and rural/forestry/coastal pilot and assessment cases. This selective overlap indicates that the integration of these three sustainability dimensions remains relatively context-specific and is perhaps dependent on particular territorial needs and actor configurations.

Importantly, the analysis reveals that none of the goals or objectives identified across the cases encompass all four pillars of sustainability—social, cultural, economic, and environmental—simultaneously. This absence suggests that, while there is a growing awareness of the multidimensional nature of sustainability, fully integrated approaches remain rare. It highlights an opportunity for future NBS initiatives to adopt more holistic frameworks that consider the full spectrum of sustainability in order to enhance their transformative potential.

5.4. Intersection between URBINAT categories and territorial typologies

The following table and diagram illustrate how the different territorial typologies of the pilot and assessment cases in the TRANS-Lighthouses project intersect with the categories of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) defined by the URBINAT project.

It is worth noting that the "Social and Solidarity Economy" category is most strongly associated with rural typologies, which also show significant engagement with the "Participatory" and "Territorial" aspects of NBS. In contrast, urban typologies are primarily linked to the "Territorial" category, followed by "Participatory" and then "Social and Solidarity Economy" aspects. Forestry areas are connected only with the "Social and Solidarity Economy" and "Territorial" categories.

The rural/urban/forestry typology is related exclusively to the "Participatory" and "Territorial" categories. Meanwhile, the rural/forestry/coastal typology reflects contributions from the "Social and Solidarity Economy," "Participatory," and "Territorial" categories. The urban/coastal typology stands out as the only one incorporating elements of the "Technological" category, in addition to "Participatory" and "Territorial" aspects. Rural/forestry areas engage mainly with "Participatory" and "Territorial" dimensions, while rural/semi-rural typologies are associated with the "Social and Solidarity Economy" and "Participatory" categories of the URBINAT NBS catalogue.

Figure 13: Distribution of the territorial typologies of the Pilots and assessments cases according to the four URBINAT categories

Territorial typology	Social and Solidarity economy	Participatory	Technological	Territorial
Rural	3	3	0	2
Urban	2	4	0	5
Forestry	1	0	0	1
Costal	0	0	0	0
Rural/Urban/Forestry	0	1	0	1
Rural/Forestry/coastal	2	2	0	2
Urban/coastal	0	1	1	1
Rural/Forestry	0	1	0	1
Rural/Semirural	2	1	0	0

Table 10: Distribution of the territorial typologies of the Pilots and assessments cases according to the four URBINAT categories

Conclusions

This report highlights the inherent challenges of applying a narrow typological framework to the definition and analysis of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). It becomes evident that NBS are inherently multi-faceted and complex, shaped by a wide array of interrelated factors. Rather than fitting neatly into restrictive categories, each NBS embodies a combination of characteristics that reflect its unique social, environmental, cultural, and economic dimensions. The typological classifications presented in this analysis serve as useful tools for examining and comparing different NBS, offering insights into some of the key aspects that must be considered during both the planning and co-creation phases of NBS development.

While the aspects explored in this report may not encompass the full range of elements that define an NBS, they provide an expanded understanding of the critical dimensions that practitioners and stakeholders should take into account. Furthermore, this research has sought to uncover interconnections between various analytical layers, including the material and immaterial components of NBS, the objectives and goals set by stakeholders, the URBINAT categories, and the territorial typologies within which the different solutions are embedded. By mapping these relationships, the study contributes to a more holistic understanding of how NBS operate within diverse socio-ecological contexts and offers a framework for more nuanced analysis and informed decision-making. Below main highlights from the analysis and the findings:

Complexity of Territorial Typologies in NBS Implementation

- The distribution of cases across territorial typologies (urban, rural, forestry, coastal) reveals a diverse but uneven representation.
- Urban contexts are the most frequently represented, suggesting a strong focus on urban sustainability challenges.
- Rural territories also feature prominently, with significant attention to ecological conservation and rural development.
- Hybrid typologies (e.g., rural/urban/forestry, rural/forestry/coastal) reflect the project's recognition of territorial complexity and overlapping socio-ecological systems.

Gaps in Territorial Representation

- Purely coastal and forestry typologies are underrepresented, pointing to potential gaps in the project's territorial coverage.

- This absence highlights the need for future research to explore NBS in coastal and forest-exclusive contexts, given their particular vulnerabilities to climate change.

Dynamic Evolution of Territorial Classifications

- The case of Cáceres demonstrates the adaptability of pilot projects: originally classified as urban, it shifted to rural due to governance challenges, leading to more effective, community-driven NBS implementation.
- This reclassification underscores the importance of flexibility and local responsiveness in territorial approaches to NBS.

Material vs. Immaterial Nature-Based Solutions

- Rural areas show the highest prevalence of immaterial NBS, focusing on social cohesion, cultural heritage, and community engagement.
- Urban and urban/coastal areas emphasize material NBS (e.g., green infrastructure) more heavily than immaterial ones.
- This distribution suggests differing priorities and strategies in urban versus rural settings.

Goals and Objectives by Territorial Typology

- Across all cases, there is a dominant focus on environmental sustainability, especially in urban and rural contexts.
- Cultural sustainability often intersects with environmental goals in rural/forestry/coastal areas, emphasizing the role of cultural identity and local knowledge.
- Social and economic sustainability goals are primarily concentrated in rural and semi-rural settings, reflecting the need for economic resilience alongside ecological initiatives.

Partial Integration of Sustainability Pillars

- No case simultaneously addresses all four pillars of sustainability (social, cultural, economic, and environmental).
- This fragmentation suggests that while multi-dimensional approaches exist, fully integrated, holistic NBS strategies are still rare, pointing to an opportunity for future NBS development.

Territorial Typologies and URBINAT Categories

- Social and Solidarity Economy aspects are most prevalent in rural settings.
- Territorial and Participatory aspects are strong across most typologies but are particularly notable in urban and mixed rural/urban/forestry settings.
- Technological innovations appear only in the urban/coastal typology, suggesting a niche for integrating tech-based NBS in complex, multi-pressure environments.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Pilot Case Estarreja Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>ECO - Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora [Collaborative and Guiding Estarreja] ECO intends to co-create a strategy for the promotion and conservation of Estarreja natural values, achieved through participatory approaches. Six LKLs will be implemented at a local-level, covering all parishes/towns of the council, and two at a council-level - one for institutions, and one exclusive for CME collaborators. These will allow a detailed co-diagnostic of the territory, the co-creation of solutions to be implemented, and the definition of frameworks/strategies for the future work on local natural patrimony. Additionally, the pilot case extends to schools, in which two 8th grade and two 11th classes are challenged to co-create NbS to implement in the council.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Estarreja Municipality CES Council parishes Schools</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Rural</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Farming / Forestry / Livestock Environmental and Tourist education Biodiversity conservation Sustainable development</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: Population of 26 224, population density of 242.4 hab/km2. 63% of its population is between 15 and 64 yo, and 24% is over 65 yo Motivation Pilot: To co-create a strategy for the promotion and conservation of Estarreja natural values with the stakeholders present in the territory. To involve local actors in biodiversity conservation, in NbS design and implementation, and in the decision-making processes. This may also improve human-nature relations in the council as well as environmental awareness. Challenges: Intensification of agricultural activities, lack of environmental awareness, profit approach in farming and forestry, large diversity of stakeholders and interests present in the territory, lack of participatory culture in the council. Existing NBS applications - The main NBS already implemented in the focus area of this pilot is BioRia, a Nature Tourism and Environmental Education project. Other relevant NbS in the council include initiatives promoted by NGOs in partnership with local governments and research organizations, for instance the micro-reserve "Lusitânica"</p>

	(Associação BioLiving) and the initiative "Plantar o Futuro" (Associação Agora Aveiro). NBS categories - Mostly Territorial and Participatory, also Social & Solidarity Economy
What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	The typologies will depend on the NbS co-created. Globally: Local communities Students
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	Local NGOs (cultural, social, sporting and environmental) Farmers Foresters Citizens Local businesses Industry Public authorities Academia Teachers Students Technicians

Annex 2: Pilot Case Barcelos Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Playground is Nature The Barcelos municipality's pilot project is entitled Playground is Nature, and will be implemented in three schools in different parishes in the municipality of Barcelos. The António Fogaça Basic School, a School Centre that covers pre-school and 1st cycle; the Abel Varzim 2,3 Basic School, with 2nd and 3rd cycle students; and the Vila Cova Basic and Secondary School, with students from 1st to 12th grade. The "Playground is Nature" pilot project has the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Co-create playground spaces through Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), involving those who use them (students, teachers and operational assistants) and a participatory process for selecting a proposal based on the students' ideas; Promote intergenerational interaction and integration as an instrument for preserving and enhancing the ecological and cultural heritage of school playgrounds; Appropriation of natural systems for human recreation; Encouraging leadership among young people and the educational community; Increasing the environmental resilience of local communities in adapting to climate change; Provide creative leisure among students, the ability to play freely and in contact with nature, autonomy in recreational relationships with sustainable playgrounds; Diversifying the sources of play and recreation among the youth community; Transmitting ancestral knowledge about free play and youth leadership.
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Barcelos Municipality CES Youth associations/groups Selected schools and teaching community Parents' Associations Cultural Environmental associations</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Forestry, Rural and Urban</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Nature as an integral part of school spaces Youth environments Climate change impact mitigation</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p><u>Data:</u>The Municipality of Barcelos had, in 2021, a population of 116.766, a density of 308 hab/km² where 24,5% of its population is below 24 years old, and 20% is over 65. The area of the pilot project is located in rural, forestry and urban areas. It has a universe of 13,765 students from pre-school to secondary education. <u>Challenges:</u></p>

	<p>Very urbanized school playgrounds, with few opportunities for contact with nature and few opportunities for creative play.</p> <p>Overly protective playgrounds, with few opportunities to experience the risks and challenges of free play in natural or less artificial environments.</p> <p>To promote climate adaptation and mitigation to climate changes.</p> <p>Stimulate the participation of the critical mass, promote environmental awareness among stakeholders and implement the NBS agreed.</p> <p>Stimulating a sense of community among the project stakeholders.</p> <p>Promote the transmission of ancestral knowledge of free play and youth leadership.</p> <p>Develop more environmentally sustainable playgrounds; diversify sources of play and recreation among the youth community.</p> <p><u>Motivation of the pilot</u> - Intergenerational interaction and integration as an instrument to preserve and enhance the ecological and cultural heritage of the school's playgrounds.</p> <p>Appropriation of the natural based systems to the human life recreation.</p> <p>Promotion of leadership with youth and educational community. Promote environmental resilience of local communities in adapting to climate change.</p> <p>Promote creative leisure among students, the ability to play freely and in contact with nature, autonomy in recreational relationships with sustainable playgrounds</p> <p><u>Define the NBS category/ies</u> of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories (Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Please select the category/ies</p> <p>As the students are at the design and proposal stage, we don't yet know all the types of NbS that will be covered. At the moment, they are Territorial.</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Students</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>Students Teachers Technicians</p>

Annex 3: Pilot Case Lagoa/Azores Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p><i>Natural Trail as a space for community wellbeing</i></p> <p>At Lagoa Municipality territory exists a natural asset called "Water trail/hells window" that belongs to the Network of Pedestrian Routes Classified by the Regional Government of the Azores, in order to ensure the safety and tranquility of hikers during their walks.</p> <p>To adapt this Trail and promote it as a NBS some steps are needed to cover different dimensions that are important to us: Trail as a space of Open Science Schooling (OSS), as space for health and wellbeing, for community development and inclusion, for art and culture and biodiversity conservation.</p> <p>To achieve these different objectives the first step is work on security dimensions.</p> <p><i>For the safety of the "Water Route Trail", it is important to start with initiatives that allow us to understand and mitigate risks associated with the use of this nature trail, as well understand the cargo capacity of the natural site and for that it is necessary to monitor local biodiversity. Here are some points that may be relevant to this project:</i></p> <p><i>a-About Trail Safety:</i></p> <p><i>Risk Perception Surveys-: Applying surveys to trail users is a way to understand how people perceive the risks associated with the trail. This can include questions about terrain conditions, signage, and other users' behavior.</i></p> <p><i>b-About Cargo Capacity:</i></p> <p>To research on Cargo Capacity we need to know how many users are at the trail every day: For that we installed Eco-Counters, which are an effective tool for monitoring the number of trail users. This can help us understand the popularity of the trail and develop a plan for improvements on accessibility infrastructure and nature conservation.</p> <p>Biodiversity Identification- Identifying the local flora is crucial to understanding the biodiversity of the area. A team dedicated to cataloguing the species found there can contribute to a valuable database that can be used for future research or conservation</p> <p><i>c-About the profile of users and know the motivation behind the decision to hike on these trail:</i></p> <p>We need to know the profile of users and their motivations: for that we have designed a series of instruments /surveys to collect data about this important dimension.</p> <p><i>d-Open Science Schooling (OSS):</i></p> <p>Learning can increasingly be carried out in three environments: formal, non-formal and informal, where different areas of society collaborate beyond strictly educational settings. Through these we can promote citizen</p>
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	<p>science and a natural platform for experiential learning as well virtual learning through our Trilho do mundo platform. https://trilhodomundo.org OSS will help us to promote activities that involve the community, schools, partners and trail users in environmental awareness, environmental education, and about the importance to preserving biodiversity can the engagement in sustainable practices</p> <p>e-Space for health and well-being</p> <p>This trail will be the site to develop activities on forest therapy like forest bath and Forest mind walks. We will conduct research to understand the impact of these natural environments on human well being. Forest and nature for human well-being has been confirmed by many studies that have been conducted in recent years and by various reports. Forest is a natural place for mental skills pursuit.</p> <p>d-The trail as an economic asset for sustainable development</p> <p>Using co-creation and participatory governance we are working neighbouring communities (lugar dos remedios) to visioning possibilities for sustainable local business and the sharing of profits generated by tourism. Local mapping using a walkthrough was conducted on the neighborhood.</p> <p>e- Connecting with nature through art and culture</p> <p>Different initiatives were organized to promote the Trail as a site for cinema, exhibitions, concerts as a strategy to approach communities with nature.,</p>
Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	Collaborative governance between University, municipality Lagoa , Kairós and environmental organisations, NGO's tourism enterprises and schools
General Typology	Coastal, Forestry, rural
Specific Types	<p>Nature and landscape as an natural asset;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sustainable Development; -Green Tourism and green economy; -Wellness through nature -Biodiversity conservation; - Art and culture on nature; -Social inclusion: nature for all; - Reciprocity between human and non human - Collaborative governance; - Open Science Schooling
Specific Info	<p><u>Data:</u> The municipality of Lagoa has 14,442 inhabitants and has a global area of 45.6km², and five parishes.</p> <p><u>Motivation of the pilot</u> -Lagoa is a small city that aims to establish a more sustainable development for a positive symbiosis of contrasts: between a past and a future, the sea</p>

	<p>and the land, the traditional and the modern that Lagoa is lived and felt. Nature is an important value in this process</p> <p><u>Challenges:</u> Trails as an active to a sustainable development based on nature.</p> <p>Lagoa is looking for a sustainable development and tourism based on nature with a focus on market segmentation, identifying "Market Niche" as a small but profitable segment of a market created by identifying needs and by offering products that satisfy them.</p> <p><u>Existing NBS applications</u> - Trails are an important asset in Lagoa. They are a NBS with a positive impact in wellness, health and economic development.</p> <p><u>Define the NBS category/ies</u> of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories (Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Please select the category/ies</p> <p>Territorial NBS; Social and Solidarity Economy NBS Participatory NBS</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users of trails. -Students and teacher's; - Tourist; -Local community; -Social work students; -Disadvantage people (like homeless, drug abusers and clients of social services).; - Artistics;
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students - Practitioners; - Researcher's - Stakeholders - Local community

Annex 4: Pilot Case Strovolos Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Systems to rehabilitate urban river space and enhance human-nature relationship Our focus is on introducing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to an existing green belt used as public space. The main goals of our pilot are: The enrichment of occupation patterns for urban green spaces. (create social spaces for the community to gather, interact, and learn for NBS) Improve well-being of users through new relationship to nature.(develop feelings of care and responsibility towards nature by engaging citizens in decision-making) Address environmental urban challenges (heat island, flooding, etc.) through the implementation of NBS (tree planting, permeable surfaces, riparian buffer zones, etc.) Biodiversity conservation as an expression of care (bird nests, pollinators hotels, ecosystem understanding) Collaborating with the Municipality of Strovolos, local NGOs, and stakeholder communities, we emphasize on engaging families, youth, residents and creative industries in co-developing the necessary conditions for change. Despite conflicting challenges, like land ownership, low participatory culture and institutional dynamics, our pilot strives to create effective and synergistic interventions in the linear park of Pedieos.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Strovolos Municipality > The Cyprus Institute
<p>General Typology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Coastal > Urban
<p>Specific Types</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Urban pressure > Improve urban Spaces > Climate change effects mitigation > Biodiversity Enhancement
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The Pedieos river in the urban area of Nicosia region is dry most of the year. Along the river, a linear park is under development with limited social spaces beyond the cyclist and pedestrian paths.</p> <p>Motivation Pilot: Mitigation of heat island effects, reduction of flooding, refuge for urban biodiversity. Heavy pressure of climate change.</p> <p>Challenge: The consolidation and improvement of the park is threatened by urbanisation pressure, expansion of roads and parking lots,</p>

	<p>degradation of semi-natural areas.</p> <p>Existing NBS applications - NBS in Nicosia: 65 organised parks have been created; More than 250 green places - 340,000m² in total; 40,000 trees were planted in public areas; 32 green areas with amphitheatres, lakes, fountains and 65 playgrounds.</p> <p>NBS Categories based on URBiNAT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Territorial > Technological > Participatory
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Authorities > NGOs / Civil Society > Local residents > Tourists > Cyclist & Joggers > Families > Youth
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Authorities > NGOs / Civil Society > Local residents > Youth

Annex 5: Pilot Case Rome Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Redesign public space The scope of the intervention is to transform two public spaces in the area of Rome San Lorenzo and Castro Laurenziano neighbourhood. The goal is to provide two different interpretations of a green classroom, broadly intended as a place for studying outdoors. One site, via De Lollis, is currently a SLOP (Space Left Over Planning) belonging to the II Municipality, the co-creation process will be held in conjunction with PhD students of the department of architecture. The second area is within the University of Sapienza Campus and will be co-create with the help of the children of the elementary school of San Lorenzo.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Rome II Municipality Univ. Sapienza Elementary School IC Tiburtina Antica</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Urban</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Urban regeneration Youth environments Climate change impact mitigation Green Classroom</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The II District has a total population of 167,649 inhabitants within a 19,66 square Km area and hosts 3,36 square Km of green area. It is one of the most densely populated in Rome (8389 inhabitants/km² - see image 03) and 68.2% of the territory consists of artificialized soils (see image 04). Parks and gardens cover a total area of 3,364 square Km, a large part of which is made up of historic gardens located in the north sectors of the District (Villa Ada, Villa Borghese and Villa Torlonia). Moreover, the population of Sapienza counts 110,000 people . (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p> <p>Motivation of the pilot - Terrains vague often characterised by the presence of archaeological areas are an opportunity to improve urban space through an innovative and inclusive approach. To inspire other actions of redevelopment of open spaces around Sapienza University. To reinvent nature in the city and establish typologies of green classrooms (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p> <p>Challenges: Mitigation of heat island effect, urban regeneration, improvement of the experience of youth in outdoor urban areas. (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p> <p>Existing NBS applications - In the area of San Lorenzo it already exists a co-created outdoor green spaces called the microforest (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p>

	Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Territorial, Social and Solidarity Economy and Participatory
What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	Students (from elementary to university), young people
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	Children, PhD Students Sapienza Undergraduate students, authorities, administration, political and elected representatives Academia, Research Teachers

Annex 6: Pilot Case Denmark/Roskilde Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Regenerative farming The key aim of the pilot is to establish a Living Knowledge Lab for Regenerative Knowledge and Practice. Within the Danish context of industrialized agriculture, we perceive regenerative farming as a framework for societally marginalized knowledges and practices, and the reemergence of these as potentials for transforming human-nature relations. Accordingly, in this pilot we find that it is key to learn from small-scale farmers lived experience with reciprocal nature relations in farming practices; to approach living knowledges and practices coherently across social, ecological and economic dimensions; develop and mature concepts and frameworks for regenerative production and lifestyles; to support regenerative practitioners and continuously develop practices and knowledges; and to identify barriers and strategies to overcome these in broader societal transformations of agricultural practices</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Univ. Roskilde/Regenerativt Jordbrug Forening (regenerative farming association)</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Rural and semi-rural</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Regenerative Farming Climate- and biodiversity crisis Socio-economic sustainability of regenerative farmers Regenerative farming transforming human-nature relations Learning from marginalized knowledges - learn from small-scale farmers lived experience</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Motivation of the pilot Facing the climate- and biodiversity crisis with this pilot we want to meet the call for a paradigm shift in farming practices- and policies from industrial towards agroecological farming. This implies a change in perceptions and practices from technological mastery over nature towards farming as reciprocally being embedded in living ecologies. Working with concrete actors in such transformation is ambivalent, conflictual and contradictory. In the pilot we will work with the re-emergence of marginalized knowledge and practices, and how regenerative farmers marginalized in the Danish context of industrialized farming, can learn from each other, inspire future farming practices, in order to scale out regenerative practices. Challenge: Understand ways for socio-economic sustainability of regenerative farming; Develop a model of</p>

	<p>decentralized collaborative governance for local small-scale farming integrating farmers, municipalities, citizens.</p> <p>Existing NBS applications - A FabLab project led by Roskilde University initiated a series of meetings between interested actors related to regenerative agriculture topic. (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p> <p>Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue :</p> <p>Participatory Solidarity economy</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Farmers Residents of rural communities Consumers</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>Academia NGO (Regenerative Farming association) Farmers Municipal actors</p>

Annex 7: Pilot Case Brussels Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Integrated Stormwater Management Flooding risks occur more and more. Mostly socially vulnerable groups live near the basins where water damage occurs the most. Giving more room to water within the city (passive approach towards water threads) by integrating NBS for water management with regard to the complex social challenges. The pilot seeks to address local socio-economic and ecological needs using Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to mitigate flooding, enhance biodiversity, and improve social cohesion in the zone PRIOR Laeken (Priority Intervention Zone), For now, the pilot actions are focused on the Verregat neighborhood in Laeken, targeting improved integrated stormwater management (ISWM) through co-creation with local residents, associations, and the Comensia social housing cooperative. This pilot Verregat's selection is based on its upstream watershed position, green infrastructure, and active community, enabling feasible infiltration projects and participatory processes. Additional initiatives may arise in other areas of PRIOR Laeken within the pilot case, where the social and environmental conditions are met.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Brussels Municipality Univ. Louvain</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Urban</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Sustainable water management > Climate change effects mitigation and adaptation > Urban pressure > Improve urban Spaces > Biodiversity Enhancement > Flood risk reduction > Urban Heat Effect Reduction
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The Brussels pilot focuses on Laeken, a densely populated area with approximately 58,000 residents, part of the City of Brussels. The neighborhood combines diverse demographics, with a mix of young families, working professionals, and older residents. Laeken is a vibrant urban district marked by challenges such as flooding risks, limited green infrastructure, and the need for better water management strategies. Motivation for the Pilot: The pilot aims to co-create solutions for integrated rainwater management by engaging local residents, schools, and</p>

	<p>associations in Laeken. This initiative seeks to foster community collaboration, improve resilience to urban flooding, and promote sustainable water practices. By involving citizens in co-designing Nature-based Solutions, the project also aims to enhance environmental awareness, strengthen the connection between people and water, and create long-term benefits for the local ecosystem and community.</p> <p>Challenges: Laeken faces multiple challenges, including recurring floods in the lowest parts of the neighbourhood, aging water infrastructure, and a lack of awareness about sustainable water management practices. The high urban density and diverse population add complexity to addressing these issues, as stakeholder interests and priorities vary significantly. Additionally, there is a need to overcome a limited participatory culture in local decision-making processes, which is crucial for the success of community-driven NbS initiatives.</p> <p>Existing NbS Applications and Categories: Current initiatives in Laeken include projects such as the creation of infiltration spaces in local parks, private gardens and green spaces, and the promotion of rainwater harvesting systems for public and private buildings. Awareness-raising activities, such as guided tours of the Sewer Museum and the "Après la Pluie" exhibition, also raise awareness about rainwater management. The Brussels pilot focuses on Territorial and Participatory NbS, emphasizing social and environmental solidarity. Territorial solutions, such as rainwater harvesting and infiltration spaces, are co-designed through participatory workshops, ensuring community involvement and sustainable outcomes.</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Citizens / Private owners Social housing tenants Young people</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>Citizens / Private owners Social housing tenants Animals (dog) Municipality Social housing agents</p>

Annex 8: Pilot Case Càcares Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Composting organic waste Decentralised composting (different from centralised composting) offers different treatments (domestic, communal, agro-composting...) closer to the places where the biowaste is generated. Decentralised composting is a synergistic successor that reduces energy consumption and transport, creates local employment and agro-ecological transition, and contributes to improving the organic culture of farmers and the quality and resilience of soil and micro-biodiversity, carbon sequestration among other synergistic environmental benefits.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Pool of municipalities of Sierra de Montánchez (province of Cáceres) like Botija, Albalá, Montánchez, Salvatierra de Santiago, Valdemorales, Zarza, among others Univ. Extremadura Economías BioRegionales *Note: we are in the process of signing a participatory agreement proposed in October 2024 to the Mancomunidad de Sierra de Montánchez (association of waste management municipalities).</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Rural Initially the pilot was planned to be 'urban/rural', and to be done with the City Council of Cáceres who neither responded nor signed the collaboration agreement presented. And at the moment, by collaborating with the pool of municipalities of Sierra de Montánchez), it has become rural.</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Decentralised management of bio-waste composting Green circular economy Territorial food systems Sustainable land and soil management in urban and rural areas Bioregional and municipal ecological-socio-economic sustainability Climate and biodiversity crisis Climatic migration Learning from marginalized knowledges Green employment for people at risk of exclusion</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The Mancomunidad Sierra de Montánchez (association of 21 rural municipalities in the south of the province of Cáceres). We elaborated a collaboration agreement focused on 7 local municipalities of the association, where local systems of decentralised composting and Living Knowledge laboratory in composting were trained and implemented.</p>

	<p>Although the agreement is not yet signed, it has been initiated from the pilot neighbourhood assemblies chaired by the mayor of information and co-designed.</p> <p>The co-design includes as part of the waste ordinances to be approved according to European and national regulations in 2025-2026.</p> <p>Motivation of the pilot - Run different models of circular economy closure on organic matter in the territory, and how to balance public and social governance, and governance model to maximise the circular flow of organic matter in Territorial Food Systems, with food and fertiliser production and soil organic matter demand.</p> <p>Challenge: Connecting organic matter management with the Food System, and not only with pure waste management. Demonstrate its positive impact on the environment.</p> <p>Existing NBS applications - The composting process is being initiated on the ground, reducing costs and emissions in a more decentralised way. On the other hand, and in line with the EU's Mission Soil line of work, increasing the low presence of organic matter, less than 2% in average arable land, sequestering carbon and increasing water resilience and micro biodiversity.</p> <p>Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories: Territorial, Participatory, and Social and Solidarity Economy</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	

Annex 9: Assessment Case Brussels Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>The Brussels assessment case addresses pressing environmental challenges, including flooding, droughts, and urban heat islands, by deploying and monitoring the Municipal Water Plan (PCE). Adopted on March 25, 2024, the PCE aims to transition Brussels into a "Water City" by 2050 through integrated water management. It defines six key water objectives, seven sub-zones, and 28 project sheets, ranging in scale from XS (stormwater management on private properties) to XL (city-wide policy actions). The Laeken area, part of the "Heysel as a sponge" sub-zone, is a focal point for implementing these strategies.</p> <p>Projects include disconnecting roofs and paved surfaces, installing rainwater tanks at schools, and large-scale public space renovations. These efforts require collaboration between municipal authorities, private actors, and local residents, highlighting the importance of engaging stakeholders to relieve pressure on sewer systems and improve rainwater management. A priority map identifies areas with the greatest flooding risks, enabling targeted interventions that align with the PCE's objectives and the overarching goal of building resilience at every scale—from individual homes to city-level initiatives.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>University of Louvain (UCL) Ville de Bruxelles - Stad Brussel (STAD BRUSSEL)</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Urban</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Sustainable water management > Climate change effects mitigation and adaptation > Urban pressure > Improve urban Spaces > Biodiversity Enhancement > Flood risk reduction > Urban Heat Effect Reduction
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data : The Brussels assessment case operates within existing governance structures, involving local stakeholders engaged in initiatives such as the Municipal Water Plan (PCE)/. The focus area is the territory of the City of Brussels that integrates diverse demographic and socio-economic profiles, with ongoing projects like Brusseau and URBiNAT fostering collaboration between public authorities, private actors, and residents.</p> <p>Motivation Assessment case: Driven by the urgent need to address environmental challenges such as floods, droughts, and urban heat islands,</p>

	<p>the assessment case in Brussels focuses on the deployment and monitoring of the Municipal Water Plan (PCE), Recognizing water as a crucial resource, the plan aims to advance Brussels towards its goal of becoming a globally renowned water city by 2050. This underscores the necessity for integrated water management within urban spaces, signalling a departure from reliance only on technological solutions to confront climate-related issues. To operationalize that, the municipal council of the City of Brussels adopted the Municipal Water Plan (GWP) on March 25, 2024.</p> <p>Challenges: The Brussels assessment faces challenges aligned with SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). These include ensuring sustainable urban development, reducing resource consumption, fostering climate adaptation, and managing conflicting priorities across diverse stakeholders.</p> <p>NBS Categories: The NBS categories applied in this assessment are Territorial. Territorial NbS involve projects such as rainwater harvesting, infiltration systems, and green-blue infrastructure. Throughout the development of the Water Municipal Plan, several working sessions have been held involving a wide range of water-related stakeholders, including the City's administrative staff, public organizations, and citizen associations, such as Vivaqua, Hydria, Perspective, Brussels-Environment, EGEB, Pool is Cool, and Coordination Senne.</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Citizens NGOs and local associations Municipality and public services</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>Municipality, public services and NGOs (citizens and non experts were specifically not integrated to the co-creation process due to the complexity of the topic but where represented by NGOs and local associations).</p>

Annex 10: Assessment Case Bologna Table

NBS Description	A new public Space in the historic center of Bologna, previously used as a parking lot. The NBS addressed the transformation of a square in the historic center of Bologna, within the University area, from a car parking lot into a pedestrian square with a temporary patch of grass to lay down and relax for people and students living and passing in the nearby. It was co-created by the students of the university of Bologna together with Fondazione Innovazione Urbana and the support of the local Municipality.
Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	Sapienza Università di Roma (UniRoma1)
General Typology	Urban
Specific Types	Tactical urbanism action Participatory workshops and transformative actions (university - municipality)
Specific Info	<p>Data: The city of Bologna had a population of approximately 392,800 residents as of December 31, 2022, a number that remained stable compared to 2021 (with an increase of about a hundred residents). However, Istat estimates that beyond the resident population, excluding tourists and those travelling for business or medical reasons, the daily population of the city exceeds 507,000 people. With over 90,000 students, the University of Bologna is one of the largest universities in Europe, of which 8,526 are international. A total of 1,036,109.13 square meters of space is allocated for teaching and extracurricular activities, distributed among the campuses in Bologna, Cesena, Forlì, Ravenna, and Rimini.</p> <p>Motivation of the assessment case: renovation of the Piazza Rossini area is the transformation of a parking area into a green area. The lack of urban green space in the city center of Bologna, intended also as places to relax, socialise, and do some physical activity, urged the transformation of piazza Rossini. (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated)</p> <p>Challenges: Good health and well-being (3 SDG); sustainable cities and communities (n. 11 SDG); life on land (n. 15).</p> <p>Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Participatory</p>
What typology/ies	Students Local citizens Tourists

of people is this NBS for?	
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	Academia, researchers Local Administration, Civil Society Students

Annex 11: Assessment Case Moisdon Lariviere Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Pioneer case of a self-sufficient and eco-community The pioneers of la Maison Autonome aim to demonstrate the feasibility of a self-sufficient lifestyle using simple and affordable technologies, while promoting a sustainable and environmentally respectful way of living. To achieve this, they have implemented Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) such as sustainable water management, permaculture, and decentralized energy production from solar panels and wind turbines.</p> <p>The case study defines its objectives by focusing on the ecological and socio-economic challenges associated with these innovative practices. The primary goal is to identify key success factors to enhance ecological resilience and address socio-economic disparities within the community, considering psychological, social, and biophysical indicators. This approach aims to establish replicable models for the pilot cases of the TRANS Lighthouses project.</p> <p>Partners are engaged in a scientific approach based on participatory processes to gather a variety of local knowledge, representations, and practices. A retrospective long-term evaluation of the psychological, social, and biophysical impacts of la Maison Autonome House is envisioned to define and disseminate effective strategies. The Case Study aims to serve as a lighthouse for the transition to resilient and autonomous communities, influencing broader changes towards sustainable development in society.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>CNRS Ecole Centrale de Nantes</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Rural</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Ecosystemic approach, long time-scale to evaluate social and ecological impacts. The potential of dissemination and adaptation of the solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -alternative ecosystem approaches for stormwater management -creation of microclimates favorable to alternative agriculture -adoption of environmentally friendly agricultural practices including food autonomy and permaculture (such as the Mandala Garden) -soil regeneration through domestic waste management and soil water purification -plant ecosystem services like phyto-depuration -low-tech energy self-production (via solar and wind technologies).

Specific Info	<p>Data: the couple and its family, participants of workshop, visitors, municipality, neighbors, other families living in eco-communities</p> <p>Motivation Pilot: Actors, the actors of their networks, their followers (coming to their training), public authorities</p> <p>Challenges: Reduced inequalities (10 SDG) ; Good Health and Well-Being (SDG 3) ; Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)</p> <p>Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue :</p> <p>Social and Solidarity Economy</p>
What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	<p>Citizen Families</p>
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	<p>Citizen Families</p>

Annex 12: Assessment Case Madrid Table

NBS Description	Composting organic waste Decentralized composting (different from centralized composting) offers different treatments (domestic, communal, agro-composting...) closer to where biowaste is generated. Decentralized composting is a synergistic successor that reduces energy consumption and transport, creates local employment and agro-ecological transition, and contributes to improving the organic culture of farmers and the quality and resilience of soil and micro-biodiversity, and carbon sequestration among other synergistic environmental benefits.
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Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	University of Extremadura (UEX) Economías BioRegionales (EBR) Community Support Agriculture (CSA) Vega de Jarama Hortaleza Composting Community
General Typology	Rural / Urban Initially, the pilot was planned to be 'urban/rural" but the research process of our assessment case is increasingly leading us to delve deeper into the specificities of the urban case, given that it is more focused on community composting as a nature-based solution to organic waste management while maintaining all the characteristics of a participatory and co-creation process. In addition to , this conceptual and methodological decision in the rural case the situation regarding agro-composting changed radically since a new law stopped the activity as we are already reflecting in our assessment report.
Specific Types	Decentralised management of bio-waste composting Green circular economy Sustainable land and soil management in urban and rural areas Bioregional and municipal ecological-socio-economic sustainability Climate and biodiversity crisis Climatic migration Green employment for people at risk of exclusion
Specific Info	Data Comunidad de Madrid Region: Rural: CSA Vega de Jarama and Urban: Composting Community at Hortaleza's neighborhood in Madrid capital Motivation Assessment: organic matter management interactions in a larger scale. bioregional networking, with and support from regional government. (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated) Challenge: sustainable cities and communities (n. 11 SDG); Responsible consumption and production (n. 12 SDG); (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated) Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Please select the category/ies - Participatory - Social and solidarity economy - Territorial

What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	Citizens (neighbours, practitioners)
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	<p>Former politicians with a ecologist and social approach (EQUO, Ahora Madrid)</p> <p>NGO's (EBR, CooperayComposta, El Olivar, San Martín de Porres)</p> <p>Primary school teachers</p> <p>Families linked to educational community (4 schools involved)</p> <p>Local markets (delivering organic waste)</p> <p>Agricultural farmers</p> <p>Students</p>

Annex 13: Assessment Case Denmark (Regenerative Farming) Table

NBS Description	<p>Innovative farming initiatives</p> <p>The key aim of the Living Knowledge(s) Lab is to support Regenerative Knowledge and Practice in Denmark. Within the Danish context of industrialized agriculture we perceive regenerative farming as a framework for societally marginalized knowledge and practices, and the reemergence of these as potentials for transforming human-nature relations.</p> <p>The Living Knowledge Lab is organized in a number of phases including both assessment and pilot activities. Both pilot and assessment activities are carried out in parallel, reinforcing each other. The assessment activities are aimed to provide background, lessons learnt and baseline information for development of pilot activities.</p>
Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	Roskilde University (RUC), Regenerative Farming association
General Typology	Rural and semi-rural
Specific Types	The same as in the pilot
Specific Info	<p>Motivation of the assessment case is to explore and analyze already existing practices of regenerative farming in Denmark, and to explore human-nature relations these practices imply which are marginalized in the context of industrial agriculture,</p> <p>Challenges: The same as the pilot</p> <p>Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Please select the category/ies</p> <p>Participatory</p> <p>Social and solidarity economy</p>
What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	<p>Farmers</p> <p>Residents of rural communities</p> <p>Consumers</p>
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	<p>Academia</p> <p>NGO (Regenerative Farming association)</p> <p>Farmers</p> <p>Municipal actors</p>

Annex 14: Assessment Case Barcelos Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Arboretum (High School of Barcelos) The Barcelos Arboretum is a botanic garden part of the green spaces of the Barcelos Secondary School. It was planted in the autumn/winter of 1986/1987 and includes woody plants restricted to the flora of Portugal mainland. It is organized according to phyto-geographical criteria of the natural forest of mainland Portugal (and not by taxonomic criteria) based on the existence of 5 poles of ecological differentiation, namely: Atlantic, Oro-Atlantic, Thermo-Atlantic, Iberian and Eu-Mediterranean. The arboretum has a didactic objective, such as supporting basic and secondary education in the municipality, as a permanent incentive to defend the natural environment; and promoting knowledge of Portuguese autochthonous flora. In one hectare we have 250 different native taxa, including some rarer bulbous plants and larger ferns, totaling 1650 individuals, among trees, shrubs and sub-shrubs. This Assessment case aims to expand 'Good Practices' and inspire replicability.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Barcelos High School Barcelos Municipality</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Urban</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Nature as an integral part of school spaces Youth environments Climate change impact mitigation</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The Municipality of Barcelos had, in 2021, a population of 116.766, a density of 308 hab/km² where 24,5% of its population is below 24 years old, and 20% is over 65. The assessment case is located inside the high school of Barcelos, predominantly in urban area. Motivation of the assessment -The Arboretum de Barcelos is a live and interactive knowledge platform that privileges research, investigation and knowledge, open to the local community and other local schools, as a focal point to environmental and science knowledge sharing. The project will be particularly relevant for the lighthouse from the perspective of people's interaction with a wide variety of existing species, in the heart of the City of Barcelos, and a source of inspiration for new SBN. Challenges: Maintenance / Funding / Opening to the community / Promotion Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories: Territorial.</p>

What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	Students
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?	Students, Teachers, Technicians

Annex 15: Assessment Case Upper Allgäu Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>On NUTS3 level (small regions) (the entire district has 1.527,97 km² , the neighbouring district of Lindau has 323 km² , the city of Kempten, 63 km² also are covered by the forest agency and work of the mountain forest initiative covers all three districts).</p> <p>Forest Regeneration, multifunctional forest management, additional aspect: creating value chains for forest products</p> <p>(Please briefly describe the NBS action)</p> <p>The aim of the district and the local administration is to enhance the situation of forests in mountain areas. The region faces challenges to adapt to climate change as impacts are amplified in mountain areas. Forests are one of the most threatened ecosystems. A lot of especially private forests are composed of planted Norway Spruce stands most affected by climate change (threats are droughts, bark beetle, storm damages due to shallow roots). The goal is to regenerate and adapt forests with more mixed tree species to adapt to climate change and at the same time providing a multitude of Ecosystem Services. A very important aspect of mountain forests is that they are important for protection against natural hazards (avalanches, floods, water storage,...)</p> <p>Challenges to change the situation are related to poor maintenance often linked to scattered small-scale ownership, lack of interest, lack of knowledge and skills. Forest Authorities realized that a change in governance is needed and shifted from a sovereign role to participatory project based approaches to address the challenges with the Mountain Forest Initiative.</p> <p>First activities in the region began as early as 1989 to reestablish a disintegrating forest at a steep mountain slope in Hinterstein exposing the village to severe threat of rockfall and avalanches. Intense activities in several project areas are ongoing for around 15 years now. Experiences with participatory approaches and forest as well as forest management as NBSs will be shared with TRL. The region and partners would like to learn from TRL to better work on challenges related to communication and outreach as a specific interest for the practitioners in the region. Challenges are to reach more forest owners and create more awareness around forests in the regional society as well as among tourists (e.g. visitor management in sensitive areas, providing knowledge as part of the educational commitment of the forest administration.</p>
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	<p>Another interesting aspect in the region could be learning opportunities about mechanisms to create regional value chains for forests and their products. Germany has a strong culture and support for forming associations and the forest sector could provide some examples for TRL on mechanisms and framing.</p>
Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	<p>Technical University of Munich (TUM), Agency for Food, Agriculture and Forestry</p>
General Typology	<p>Forestry</p>
Specific Types	<p>Knowledge and taking action in forests and forest management in mountain areas as NBS; building and creating networks to develop regional value chains for forest, timber and end users Broad range of topics relevant for TRL for analysing lessons learned - e.g. communication, learning, involving children and adolescents, forest owners to broader public, shift in Governance model, from top down to collaborative NBS: multifunctional mountain forest management as NBS, forests as NBS, especially in terms of reducing risks of natural hazards. Discussions and activities are linked also with interests in mountain areas, e.g. cattle keeping, tourism, outdoor recreation, hunting with numerous institutionalized, NGOs and non-organized stakeholders</p>
Specific Info	<p>Data: The Upper Allgäu pre-alpine and alpine areas from 630 m to 2600 m above sea level. The Iller River runs through the district from south to north. The city of Kempten with around 68 000 inhabitants is the largest city in the region. Motivation of the assessment – Retrospective Learning case: Changing paradigms and understanding of authorities changing from top-down (sovereign role) towards collaborative governance (partners of forest owners) , variety of management activities; a key issue for the area is to learn more about communication, outreach and tools. Responsible consumption and production (n. 12 SDG); climate action (13), many others are also relevant for this case, e.g. education. (Please check if this info are still relevant/updated) Define the NBS category/ies of your action according to the URBINAT definition of NBS categories(Territorial, Technological, Social and Solidarity Economy, Participatory) in this catalogue : Please select the category/ies Territorial NBS, work with forest and forest management to enhance biodiversity, resilience to climate change, flash floods, water retention, water storage, soil erosion, avalanches, landslides.</p>

	<p>Note that most of the URBiNAT catalogue is for small scale interventions and the Upper Allgäu case could be the one to "translate" them into the context of the larger countryside and forest management - very many activities and management practices could be or are NbS - e.g. magnify /are large scale interventions of described activities in urban areas, mirror things or can be put to different contexts.</p> <p>To some extent also social and solidarity economy aspects are visible in the area: Actors from the forest and timber sector are building networks (e.g. Holzforum Allgäu) to create local value chains for forest, timber and end products (e.g. school built with timber from local forests), district heatings operated with wood chips from local forests etc.</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Main idea is to provide healthy forests providing a multitude of ecosystem services for future generations to have as many or more opportunities and benefits from forest and having a better place to live) , long benefits from decisions and management actions taken now might materialize only after decades or centuries (trees need >100 years until the tree gets mature and can be used e.g. as a log for building a roof or a house)</p> <p>authorities, administration: Forest administration as stimulator and organizer to start processes together with advisory board political and elected representatives Want to address problems and solve issues about forests in their community, (degradation, loss of biodiversity, conflicts with recreational uses, hunting, ..., important aspect is if forests are not well maintained, increasing risk of natural hazards such as rock fall, landslides, flooding) community is often also one of the forest owners but broader action is needed together with other private owners - also sometimes "champion" motivating others for action</p> <p>NGOs/Civil Society Main actors: Nature conservation (biodiversity, wildlife habitats, management) and representatives (also having a Nature Experience Centre with offers) for outdoor recreation (climbing clubs, mountain bike associations; "hybrid": German Alpine Club other group such as hunting associations</p> <p>Businesses/Economy (Small/medium enterprises; bigger ones Forest owners, farmers (especially those depending on generating significant income from forest and farming); to a lesser/small extent, tourism associations, local business marketing association, entrepreneurs and construction, building companies (at more advanced stages e.g. when discussing construction of trails or stand management)</p>

	<p>Academia, Research Involved for monitoring and providing evidence-based data, but could be more as quite away from universities with respective disciplines</p> <p>Students Some involved e.g. through theses or project work, but relatively few due to distance to university with related subjects Quite a lot of work with schools and through nature park (partner school programs), a lot of environmental education activities, also some outreach to adolescents and training programs with companies such as Bosch</p> <p>Children A lot of environmental interpretation activities users of trails</p> <p>Tourists Relevant as users of the forest but very difficult to reach, yet to engage - visitor management concepts, trail information, offers by the nature park on informing about the nature; also mountain farming museum has exhibit and items to forestry and information about the mountain forests and the Mountain Forest Initiative; ideas exist to engage tourists (e.g. plant a tree) to create "customer relation" and encourage to come back. but would need to be developed</p> <p>teachers important group as the ones who drive things like partner school programs and fill things with life, reach out for educational programs and use resources such as Nature Park offers</p> <p>phd students Lack, as away from respective universities, local university of applied sciences is focussed on engineering and "hard" tourism with main focus on hospitality management and economical aspects/traditional tourism</p> <p>Practitioners See above - main group would be foresters and forest owners with abilities to manage forests themselves</p> <p>families Offers through nature park and its activities in the nature park building, exhibition and activities; also nature experience centre by NGO offers programs</p> <p>agricultural farmers See above local markets Local initiative to bring together stakeholders from the forest and timber value chain (forest owners, timber</p>
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	<p>harvesting/hauling, sawmills, carpenters), very active with projects and ideas, some nice examples, e.g. wooden buildings made from local timber, "Green Centre" (where forest administration and forest related groups are based), nature park building, local school,...</p> <p>Technicians See above</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>authorities, administration Most active groups, develop further ideas from tables, organize moderation, provide information, initiate and bring together actors (also based on access to information such as ownership of land etc., organizing invitations or voting for representatives to be at the table, information in official channels, etc.</p> <p>political and elected representatives Important to motivate on project area level, as community/village is starting point, also interest of being role model with their community, solve problems related to forest/recreation,</p> <p>NGOs/Civil Society Represent interests, e.g. advocate for nature conservation and concepts, can be supportive for action (e.g. visitor management, more natural species, more mixed stands) but also in conflict with management proposals (e.g. trail/access, management of forests vs. conservation when e.g. focus is reducing hazards on slopes); recreation, supportive or challenging partner, e.g. climbing/hiking/mountain biking vs. protection of a forest and closure of trails to create wildlife habitats; Alpine Club as a hybrid (both as advocate for conservation and recreational use) Hunting associations, depending on persons in the area - stretching from very good cooperation to active, relevant blockers</p> <p>Businesses/Economy (Small/medium enterprises; bigger ones Outside farming and forest owners, neutral experts and the ones doing management or building</p> <p>Academia, Research Provision of expertise and monitoring, also moderation, but could be more from my perspective as area is quite away from respective universities and knowledge providers Students A lot of environmental interpretation activities including planting etc.</p>

	<p>children A lot of environmental interpretation activities including planting etc. Not engaged but a challenge sometimes (e.g. overuse, trampling, ignoring rules), attempts to inform and educate with offers (information boards, nature park centre, offers for tours and experiences, exhibition in the Mountain Farming Museum)</p> <p>users of trails Tourists, families Teachers Especially through engagement and organizing environmental programs with their pupils, quite active in terms of partner schools etc.; could be perhaps even more in terms of real co-creation of designing measures and ideas.</p> <p>phd students Some activities, but very little</p> <p>practitioners</p> <p>agricultural farmers Land owners are decisive, without their will or agreement, no action will take place. Several forest owners are farmers and offer farm holidays, a few still full-time and have skill and knowledge to manage, but quite often little awareness of climate change and impact on forests, stick to narratives on best tree species and current market situations, majority is part time farmers besides a job in service or industry, an increasing number of forest owners (about half) are not related to farm and in many cases, no/little skills and possibilities to work in the forests themselves, also a significant number does not live close to the forests any more (e.g. have moved to cities like Munich)</p> <p>Local markets For timber, start to play a more important role as awareness for local, environmental products with small carbon footprint increases., active initiatives to raise awareness, e.g. stands at festivities, good practice examples etc.</p> <p>technicians</p>
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Annex 16: Assessment Case Troodos Table

NBS Description	Rural communities cultural landscape. Communal maintenance of mountain terraces, using local expert knowledge to maintain and transfer the traditional knowledge of dry stone wall construction
Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)	> The Cyprus Institute (Cyl)
General Typology	> Rural > Forestry
Specific Types	> Co-creation of knowledge and community empowerment. > Construction activities contribute to the reduction of soil erosion, conserve productive agricultural land and maintain cultural landscape.
Specific Info	Data: Troodos Mountains are the central mountain massif of Cyprus, covering nearly 30% of the Republic and accommodating more than 100 small rural communities. Motivation of the assessment: The research team and a local SME invite the community council to host a terrace construction and maintenance event. Challenges: The main concern of farmers and farm managers is agricultural production. Maintenance of drystone terraces is not their first priority. Terrace maintenance requires hard and dedicated manual labor. Many farmers are elderly and agricultural land is slowly abandoned. The number of older generation farmers with dry-stone terrace wall construction skills that can be actively involved as leaders in dry-stone wall terrace construction events is diminishing. An institutional framework needs to be developed to oversee dry-stone wall construction training activities.. The Troodos assessment case addresses the Sustainable Cities and Communities (n. 11 SDG) and Life on the Land (n. 15 SDG) NBS Categories based on URBiNAT:: > Territorial > Participatory
What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?	> Local residents > Agricultural farmers
What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the	> Authorities > Local residents > Agricultural farmers > Academia, Research > NGOs / Civil Society

co-creation process?	
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Annex 17: Assessment Case Lagoa Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>Natural Trails as a tool to reconnect with nature The NBS action has focused on the development of a participatory culture for the creation of a more inclusive trail, from which new relationships between nature and the surrounding community and its users are co-constructed. Using this approach, the NBS aims to inform and contribute to local public policies. This includes meetings with stakeholders (including a participatory workshop/focus group), group activities named "We are Nature!" that involves working with local schools and NGOs; Walkthrough involving students, questionnaires/interviews to develop the cultural mapping, monitor the governance model and the human-nature relations, and open events for the community (e.g: Night Cinema), among other actions.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Main partners: a. Municipality of Lagoa; b. University of Azores; c. KAIRÓS – Solidarity Economy Initiatives Incubation Cooperative. Other partners: OGVA, Expolab, Cefal, Vaga, ARRISCA, ONGs like "Casa do Povo de Água de Pau" CDIJ - "Youth Inclusion Development Center" Local schools Parish council</p>
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Forestry / Rural/ Coastal</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<p>Trails have a positive impact in wellness, health, economic development, citizen science, art, culture, and awareness of nature conservation</p>
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The municipality of Lagoa, occupying 46 km² of surface area, has a population of 14,189 people (50,8% being women). In 2021, 10.6% of the population on the island of São Miguel lived in Lagoa, making it the third largest municipality. Lagoa is a territory with a population density of 322,7 inhabitants/km² and is considered a municipality with a large young population – in 2022, there were 80,2 elderly people for every 100 young people. Lagoa has an active population of 10,024 people, with the activity rate in the municipality being 70.6% (Census, 2021). Motivation of the assessment: Regional or local trails need to be adapted to include other possibilities to use. For that it is</p>

	<p>necessary to evaluate risk, disaster management, rescue, local perceptions about the trail etc. Our key goal is to integrate the experience of the trail as an asset and because of that an component for local sustainable development. At the same time, we want to assess how the local community may benefit from a) the nature-human relationship/nature exposure inherent to the trail's use and b) economic value that could potentially accrue from economic activities based on the trail; c) how to increase the both the hikers and local population awareness of nature conservation. The natural environment around the trail could be an open space site for art and culture.</p> <p>Challenges: Responsible consumption and production (n. 12 SDG). Environmental vulnerability of the trail, impacted by human activities such as agriculture/cattle production and an increased pressure from tourism.</p> <p>Define the NBS category in this catalogue : Territorial; Social and Solidarity Economy; Participatory</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>1-Lagoa community and the Azorean/ Portuguese population, in general; 2- Trail users: 2.1-Tourists, expert and occasional hikers; 2.2-island Inhabitants from Lagoa and other municipalities. 2.3-People looking to reconnect with nature/benefit from ecotherapies, e.g. forest bathing);</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>University of the Azores Local and regional NGOs/Third sector (including ENGO) Local and regional power/authorities Local stakeholders Healthcare professionals Lagoa's Youth School community Local community</p>

Annex 18: Assessment Case Estarreja Table

<p>NBS Description</p>	<p>BioRia BioRia is a program focused on Nature Tourism, Environmental Education and Nature Conservation, created by the Municipality of Estarreja. The implementation of nature trails that cross the territory in all of its dimensions (natural, farming, forestry and residential areas) enables citizens and visitors to get to know the region and its natural values, promoting the contact with nature, and boosting outdoors leisure and sporting activities. These are also stage for Environmental Education and Nature Conservation activities, that allow the involvement of different target groups, from students (pre-school to universities) to the general public (citizens and tourists), and marginalized groups such as elders, ethnic minorities, and people with disabilities. All activities either are free, or require only a symbolic fee to register. Also, two of Estarreja's flagship events are linked with BioRia, namely ObservaRia and BioRace.</p>
<p>Partners (Municipalities/ Universities/ NGOs etc)</p>	<p>Throughout the 20 years of BioRia, different collaborations were established, some on a regular basis, while other in a sporadic manner. Some of the partners/partner typologies are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local parishes - Environmental NGOs - Local and regional social NGOs - Universities (namely Aveiro, Porto and Coimbra) - PACOPAR - Local cultural NGOs - Schools - Free-time activities Centres - Landowners - Farmers - Local businesses
<p>General Typology</p>	<p>Rural</p>
<p>Specific Types</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental Education - Nature tourism (trails) - Biodiversity conservation - Outdoor leisure and sports - Sustainable development - Science communication - Environmental volunteering
<p>Specific Info</p>	<p>Data: The Estarreja council covers an area of 108 km², and hosts a population of 26 584 individuals, which translates into a population density of 246 ind./km² (Censos 2021). Since 2013 the council has been divided into five parishes, namely Avanca, Pardilhó, Salreu, União de Freguesias de Beduído e</p>

	<p>Veiros and União de Freguesias de Canelas e Fermelã. The majority of the council spreads on a rural matrix, in which residential areas interconnect with gardens, crop fields, pastures and production forests.</p> <p>Although BioRia is a municipal program acting at a council level, and present in all its parishes with eight different trails, its focus area is centered in the lower region of the municipality, most of which is comprised in the Natura 2000 site of the Aveiro Lagoon, classified as a Special Area of Conservation and a Special Protection Area for birds.</p> <p>Motivation of the assessment case: BioRia was created under the motto "Conhecer para preservar" [know it, to protect it]. Two of the main goals of BioRia are to provide means to visit the council's natural values, and to share knowledge about it and communicate its richness and importance. These, in addition to practical conservation actions, aim to protect local biodiversity and ecosystems.</p> <p>Challenges: Good health and well-being (3 SDG); Quality Education (3 SDG); sustainable cities and communities (11 SDG); life on land (15 SDG).</p> <p>NBS category/ies: Territorial, Participatory</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people is this NBS for?</p>	<p>Mostly citizens overall, children and students, but also elders, people with disabilities, youth, NGOs.</p>
<p>What typology/ies of people are/were involved in the co-creation process?</p>	<p>Municipality, technicians, NGOs, Universities</p>

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Text

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